

Engineering Optical and Mirror Bi-stability Mechanically

Muhammad Junaid Khan

Department of Electronics

Quaid-i-Azam University, Islamabad, Pakistan

A Thesis Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements for the Degree
of

Master of Philosophy in Electronics

September, 2023

DEPARTMENT OF ELECTRONICS
QUAID-I-AZAM UNIVERSITY
ISLAMABAD, PAKISTAN

A thesis entitled *Engineering Optical and Mirror Bi-stability Mechanically* by Muhammad Junaid Khan in partial fulfilment of the requirements for the degree of Master of Philosophy, has been approved and accepted by the following,

Supervisor

Dr. Farhan Saif (POP, S.I)
Professor
Department of Electronics
Quaid-i-Azam University
Islamabad, Pakistan

Chairman

Dr. Qaiser Abbas Naqvi
Professor
Department of Electronics
Quaid-i-Azam University
Islamabad, Pakistan

*Dedicated to my loving parents
whose prayers and support have always been my strength,
and to my beloved country, Pakistan.*

Acknowledgements

I would like to express my deepest gratitude to the Almighty for His countless blessings, guidance, and strength throughout my academic journey, which made the completion of this thesis possible.

I am profoundly grateful to my supervisor, Dr. Farhan Saif, for providing me with the opportunity to work under his mentorship. His insightful guidance, continuous encouragement, and constructive feedback at every stage were instrumental in shaping this work. It has been a great honor to be his student.

I would also like to extend my sincere thanks to Dr. Hassan Mahmood for his motivation and inspiration towards research, which greatly influenced my academic growth. My heartfelt appreciation goes to my colleagues and peers, whose support, discussions, and assistance were invaluable in overcoming challenges encountered during this work.

I am forever indebted to my parents for their unwavering love, sacrifices, and encouragement, which have been the cornerstone of my achievements. Lastly, I would like to thank all my friends, relatives, and well-wishers who, directly or indirectly, contributed to the successful completion of this thesis.

Muhammad Junaid Khan
September 01, 2023

بِسْمِ اللَّهِ الرَّحْمَنِ الرَّحِيمِ

إِنَّ فِي خَلْقِ السَّمَاوَاتِ وَالْأَرْضِ وَاخْتِلَافِ اللَّيْلِ وَالنَّهَارِ وَالْفُلْكِ الَّتِي تَجْرِي فِي الْبَحْرِ بِمَا يَنْفَعُ
النَّاسَ وَمَا أَنْزَلَ اللَّهُ مِنَ السَّمَاءِ مِنْ مَّاءٍ فَأَحْيَا بِهِ الْأَرْضَ بَعْدَ مَوْتِهَا وَبَثَّ فِيهَا مِنْ كُلِّ
دَابَّةٍ وَتَصْرِيفِ الرِّيَّاحِ وَالسَّحَابِ الْمُسَخَّرِ بَيْنَ السَّمَاءِ وَالْأَرْضِ لَآيَاتٍ لِقَوْمٍ يَعْقِلُونَ ○
(الْبَقَرَةُ : 164)

Verily, in the creation of the heavens and the earth, and in the alternation of the night and the day, and in the ships (and vessels) which sail through the ocean carrying cargo profitable for the people, and in the (rain) water which Allah pours down from the sky, reviving therewith the earth to life after its death, and (the earth) in which He has scattered animals of all kinds, and in the changing wind directions, and in the clouds (that trail) between the sky and the earth, duty-bound certainly, (in these) are (many) signs for those who put their reason to work.

(Al-Baqarah : 164)

Abstract

We present a theoretical investigation of hybrid nano-electro-optomechanical bistable behavior in a modulated nano-transducer system. The setup comprises a Fabry-Pérot cavity driven by a strong pump laser and a weak probe field, giving rise to radiation-pressure-induced optomechanical coupling in the presence of tunable Coulomb interaction between mechanical elements in a *nano-electro-opto-mechanical system* (NEOMS). The interplay of these couplings introduces strong nonlinearities that yield optical bistability in the intracavity photon population and mechanical bistability in the steady-state mirror positions. The system maintains coherence by effectively minimizing environmental noise. Furthermore, we show that external modulating fields applied to the movable mirrors enable precise control over both optical and mechanical bistability. These findings offer promising prospects for designing tunable electro-opto-mechanical switches and optical transistors, as well as for manipulating the frequencies and group velocity of light pulses in applications relevant to quantum information processing (QIP).

Keywords *Nano-electro-optomechanical system (NEOMS), Optical bistability, Mechanical bistability, Optomechanical coupling, Coulomb interaction, Quantum information processing, Slow light.*

Contents

Contents	ii
List of Figures	iv
List of Abbreviations	1
1 Introduction	2
2 Nano-Opto-Electro-Mechanical Systems	5
2.1 The Physical System	6
2.2 The Mechanical Oscillator	6
2.3 The Optical Resonator	9
2.4 The Hamiltonian	12
2.5 Quantum Langevin Equations	14
2.6 Quantum Fluctuations and Noise in the Heisenberg-Langevin Framework	15
2.7 The Model	18
2.8 Total Hamiltonian of the System	19
2.9 Mirror and Field Hamiltonian	19
2.10 Driving Field Hamiltonian	20
2.11 Interaction Hamiltonian	21
3 Optical Bi- Stability Results	24
3.1 Intra-Cavity Photon Number	26
3.2 Effect of external mechanical driving fields on optical bistability	28

CONTENTS

4 Bose-Einstein Condensate in Nano-Electro-Optomechanics	30
4.1 Basic Theory and System Model	30
4.1.1 System Model	31
4.1.2 Mathematical Treatment	32
4.1.3 Optomechanical Bose-Hubbard Hamiltonian	33
4.1.4 Linearized Dynamics of the System	35
4.1.5 Definition of Key Parameters and Ansatz for Fluctuations	37
4.1.6 Matrix Formulation of the Linearized System	38
4.1.7 Solution for the Cavity Fluctuation Amplitude	39
4.1.8 Output Field and Optical Response	40
4.1.9 Transmission of the Probe Field	42
4.1.10 Experimental Parameters	42
4.1.11 Simulations and Electromagnetically Induced Transparency (EIT)	42
4.1.12 Slow Light in Bose-Einstein Condensates	44
4.2 Conclusion	47
5 Conclusion	48
Appendix A: Bistability Simulation Code	50
A.1 Python Implementation	50
Bibliography	54

List of Figures

2.1	The optomechanical cavity length L is modulated by optical field, that causes a modulation of amplitude X_m . we express the incident optical field as ϵ_p , the output field ϵ_{out} and the length of the cavity as L	6
2.2	The schematics of an electromechanical setup. The capacitance $C(X_m)$ of the LC resonator is modulated by the mechanical motion.	7
2.3	The schematic of the Nano-Electro-Opto-Mechanical system. The mechanical resonator MR_1 is connected to the cavity field via optomechanical coupling represented by g_0 , and the second mechanical resonator MR_2 through the strength of Coulomb coupling, g_c . An input laser field with amplitude ϵ_l and a probe field with amplitude ϵ_p are introduced into the cavity through the fixed mirror. Furthermore, MR_1 is influenced by the biased voltage $+V_1$, while MR_2 is influenced by the biased voltage $-V_2$. In this context, L signifies the cavity's length, ϵ_1 and ϵ_2 refer to the external driving fields on MR_1 and MR_2 respectively, ϵ_{out} pertains to the output probe field, and γ_1 and γ_2 denote the mirror decay rates.	20
3.1	The average intracavity photon number $ C_s ^2$, in relation to the driving laser power, \wp_l . These results are obtained using specific system parameters for this scenario, including $m_1 = m_2 = 145$ ng and $\omega_1 = \omega_2 = 947$ kHz, $\epsilon = \epsilon = 0$, and $G_0 = 2\pi \times 215$ kHz.	27

LIST OF FIGURES

4.1	Schematic of the NEOMS with a trapped BEC: The movable mirror MR_1 interacts with the cavity field via radiation-pressure optomechanical coupling, while the cavity field also couples to the two-level atoms of the BEC with atomic coupling strength g . The mechanical resonators MR_1 and MR_2 are coupled through a tunable Coulomb interaction g_c , with MR_1 charged by a bias voltage V_1 and MR_2 by $-V_2$. The cavity mode is driven through the fixed mirror by a strong pump laser of amplitude ϵ_l and a weak probe field of amplitude ϵ_p . L denotes the cavity length, ϵ_1 and ϵ_2 are external driving fields applied to MR_1 and MR_2 , respectively, and r_0 is the equilibrium distance between the two mechanical resonators.	31
4.2	Absorption and dispersion spectra of the EIT window as a function of normalized detuning δ/ω_1	43
4.3	Transmission phase $\phi(\omega_p)$ vs normalized detuning δ/ω_1	45
4.4	Group delay τ (μ s) vs pump power P_l (mW) for cavity decay rates $\kappa = 2\pi \times 215$ kHz and $\kappa = 3\pi \times 215$ kHz.	46

List of Abbreviations

EIT	Electromagnetically Induced Transparency: A quantum interference effect that renders an otherwise opaque medium transparent to a probe laser field.
BEC	Bose-Einstein Condensate: A state of matter formed by bosonic atoms cooled to near absolute zero, where a macroscopic number of atoms occupy the same quantum state.
NOEMS	Nano-Opto-Electro-Mechanical Systems: Nanoscale systems integrating optical, mechanical, and electrical components for controlling light-matter interactions.
NEOMS	Nano-Electro-Opto-Mechanical Systems: Hybrid nanoscale systems combining optical cavities, mechanical resonators, and electric control for enhanced optomechanical coupling.
QED	Quantum Electrodynamics: The quantum field theory describing interactions between light (photons) and matter (charged particles).

Chapter 1

Introduction

The study scientific knowledge light, has been a cornerstone of physics since its inception. Light recognized as made of photons. It exhibits both classical and quantum phenomena. The interactions between light and matter at the smallest scale. [1–3] is topic interest. The momentum carried by electromagnetic field applies a force through radiation pressure, inducing movement in the confining mirror of the cavity. This radiation pressure force leads to changes in the position of the movable mirror. Consequently, the optical path experiences a displacement, ultimately introducing non-linear characteristics to the system. This non-linear phenomenon gives rise to different non-classical aspects like optical bistability, resembling the non-linearity found in Kerr-medium situations[4–7].

The pressure force from the light affects both the optical and mechanical parts of a cavity resonator [8–10]. Such as transparency created by optomechanical effects and the process of Four-Wave Mixing. Researchers have formed hybrid quantum systems [11–13], by combining optomechanical resonators with different elements such as mechanical membranes [14–18], Bose-Einstein condensates or Fermions individual atoms with multiple energy levels, and combining opto-mechanical systems and electro-mechanical systems [19–21]. In these hybrid system, the special quantum traits of both mechanical and electronic parts become important. Wineland [22, 23] and his team were the first to notice these system, and then Zoller, Tian, Milburn, and colleagues developed the study terminology.

The optical cavity field acts in a non-linear way, creating optical bistability in the system. This results in a specific occurrence called hysteresis [24]. Researchers have studied the optical bistability that comes from the Kerr effect. They looked at this in a simple optomechanical system and also in mixed optomechanical systems containing trapped cold atoms [25–28] and two-level atoms[28]. Additionally, researchers have looked into this phenomenon in a mixed electro-optomechanical system where nanomechanical resonators[29] are connected.

Optical bistability could be useful in nonlinear quantum optics tasks like handling optical signals [30], creating optical switches [31], and making devices for optical communication[32][17, 33–37]. Combine an optomechanical system and an electromechanical system to create a small device that converts electrical and optical signals. The new nano system called nano-electro-optomechanical system (NEOMS) is created using two charged mechanical resonators named MR1 and MR2. The field of light inside the optical cavity is connected to MR1 by using a link that combines optics and mechanics. We apply two outside voltages, $+V_1$ and $-V_2$, to the mechanical resonators MR1 and MR2. This makes the resonators interact with each other through Coulomb coupling. We make the light inside the probe switch between two states and control the mirror's back-and-forth movement in the nano mirrors MR1 and MR2. We do this by changing the strength of signals that we apply only to the mechanical resonators.

Scientists have created a system where light and mechanics work together using things like two small spinning disks, a nano crystal beam, or a microwave with two small moving beams [38, 39]. We have used powerful mechanical forces to create devices that mix quantum spins photon devices [40] and vibrations, as well as to achieve very strong connections between exciton photon coupling [41] and vibrations. Scientists have studied a situation called optical bi-stability in different opto mechanical systems [26, 42–48] where light and mechanics interact. This happens because of a push from the light's pressure inside an optical cavity. We also introduce a controllable switch that works by controlling the two-state behavior under different test conditions.

We figure out the rules that control how the system works, including the

CHAPTER 1. INTRODUCTION

total Hamiltonian and Heisenberg Langevin equations that explain how things move, and then we find solutions where everything stays stable and consistent. We study how the number of photons inside the system's Intra cavity photon number between two states, with the help of two outside forces applied to the nano mechanical mirrors MR1 and MR2. we look at how the positions where the nano mechanical mirrors MR1 and MR2 can switch between two states when we use outside signals to change them.

Chapter 2

Nano-Opto-Electro-Mechanical Systems

The NOEMS main objective is to create innovative systems and devices with special characteristics and events that occur at the nanoscale. NOEMS has the potential to enable a wide range of applications like imaging, communication, sensing and computation, among others, by merging optical, electrical, and mechanical functions. Controlling the propagation of light is one of the most significant issues in optics and photonics, optical communications like modulation, optical switching, device and network reconfigurability in addition to imaging and sensing (such as beam steering). Nano-opto-electro-mechanical systems (NOEMS), In the field of nanophotonics considered one of the new platforms for researching mechanical and electrical freedoms, over the last few years, has seen rapid growth. Using the optical, mechanical and electronic degree of freedom in NOEMS offers exciting opportunities to handle information carriers, Here, it investigates the motion of light, flow of electrons, and mechanical vibration modes we see in both classical and quantum worlds. NOEMS concepts and technologies, high speed and low-power consumption switches, high-efficiency microwave-optical conversion devices, and multiple quantum information processing functions can be applied to its on-chip integration.[49, 50] The principles of NOEMS will introduce, the most recent advancements, important achievements.

2.1 The Physical System

In 2015, Markus Aspelmeyer et al. Although optomechanical system exist in real world application. By using a simple one oscillator mirror in the Fabry-Perot cavity, it is most fundamental model connected two harmonic oscillators. In this section introduce its primary components the optical and mechanical resonator. The physical back ground of the optical and mechanical interaction[51].

Figure 2.1: The optomechanical cavity length L is modulated by optical field, that causes a modulation of amplitude X_m . we express the incident optical field as ϵ_p , the output field ϵ_{out} and the length of the cavity as L .

2.2 The Mechanical Oscillator

It has been experimentally demonstrated that mechanical oscillators generally possess a large number of mechanical eigenmodes due to the high number of degrees of freedom and their size, whose geometry, material characteristics, and the coupling to its support are responsible for its spectral features. In general, a displacement field can be used to define the form of the spatial mechanical mode $u(r, t)$ [52]. The $u(r, t)$ can be expanded in terms of the oscillators eigen modes $u_n(r)$ and its related time-dependent amplitudes $X_n(t)$.

$$u(r, t) = \sum_n X_n(t) u_n(r), \quad (2.1)$$

Although the response of mechanical oscillators to applied forces is not linear but linearity offers a decent approximation for the tiny displacements and is often achievable in normal operation. The amplitude $X_n(t)$ is modeled with damped harmonic oscillation.

The damping component simultaneously serves as a temperature of the environment known as a "heat bath" and a source of noise for the mechanical oscillator, illustrates the coupling of the mechanical oscillator to its support.

Figure 2.2: The schematics of an electromechanical setup. The capacitance $C(X_m)$ of the LC resonator is modulated by the mechanical motion.

The impact of the heat bath is modeled as a many harmonic oscillators in the group of infinitely in a thermal state at a temperature T . A Bose-Einstein distribution is followed by the mean bath occupation number and we have

$$n_B(\omega) = [e^{\hbar\omega/K_B T} - 1]^{-1}, \quad (2.2)$$

Here \hbar and K_B represent the reduced Plank's constant and Boltzmann's constant respectively.

The mean bath occupancy at the mechanical frequency is

$$\bar{n} = n_B(\omega_m), \quad (2.3)$$

We can approximate $n_B(\omega_m)$ in the high-temperature limit with the help of the following relation

$$n_B(\omega) \approx \frac{K_B T}{\hbar\omega_m}, \quad (2.4)$$

The mechanical quality factor is defined as

$$Q_m = \frac{\omega_m}{\gamma_m}, \quad (2.5)$$

The quality factor and thermal decoherence rate are related as

$$\bar{n}\gamma_m \approx \frac{K_B T}{\hbar Q_m}, \quad (2.6)$$

To get minimal thermal decoherence, we require a high-Q mechanical oscillator and a low-temperature bath, which can be produced through cryogenic cooling of the experimental equipment.

For the quantum treatment of the mechanical oscillator we introduce position and momentum operators X_m, P_m , which fulfill canonical commutation relations $[X_m, P_m] = i\hbar$. We also introduce the dimensionless quadrature, as is typical in quantum optics $[x_m, p_m] = i$. They can also be defined in terms of creation and annihilation operators c_m^\dagger, c_m

$$[c_m, c_m^\dagger] = 1, \quad (2.7)$$

$$x_m = \frac{c_m + c_m^\dagger}{\sqrt{2}}, \quad (2.8)$$

$$p_m = \frac{c_m - c_m^\dagger}{\sqrt{2}l}, \quad (2.9)$$

By re-scaling the mechanical variables with the ground state amplitude x_0 of the oscillator, the dimensionless position and momentum operators can be defined as

$$X_m = \sqrt{2} x_0 x_m, \quad (2.10)$$

$$P_m = \sqrt{2} m_{\text{eff}} \omega_m x_0 p_m, \quad (2.11)$$

where x_0 represents the zero-point motion of the mechanical oscillator and is given by

$$x_0 = \sqrt{\frac{\hbar}{2m_{\text{eff}}\omega_m}}. \quad (2.12)$$

Here, m_{eff} is the effective mass of the mechanical mode and ω_m is its resonance frequency. This rescaling allows the mechanical operators X_m and P_m to be expressed in dimensionless units, which is particularly convenient for quantifying optomechanical interactions in terms of the oscillator's quantum ground state.

2.3 The Optical Resonator

The second essential element in a cavity-optomechanical system is the optical cavity. This cavity acts as a container (Resonator) for photons that resonate within it. An example of such a cavity is the straightforward Fabry–Pérot cavity, which consists of two mirrors with high reflectivity placed L units apart. This arrangement results in a series of evenly spaced modes with distinct resonance frequencies, and the intervals between these frequencies are referred to as the free spectral range. The value of the free spectral range is defined by the length of the cavity no presence of an optical medium.

$$\nu_n = n\Delta\nu, \quad \Delta\nu = \frac{c}{2L}, \quad (2.13)$$

In which a mechanical oscillator interact with a single cavity mode pos-

sessing a specific angular frequency denoted as $\omega_c = 2\pi\nu_c$. This particular configuration can be readily established through experimentation in setups involving nanoscale and microscale optomechanics. Consequently, interactions between distinct cavity modes are absent, as they do not couple with the mirror. However, it's worth noting that in certain systems, intentional or perturbative coupling can indeed take place between various optical modes.

$$F_{cav} = \frac{2\pi\Delta\nu}{\kappa} = \frac{\pi C}{\kappa L}, \quad (2.14)$$

Here κ represents the energy decaying rate that gives the number of photons in the cavity per unit time. Monitoring the output light of the cavity is a must for nearly every experiment if we are to distinguish between pure photon losses absorption, scattering, and transmission into the external field which we can finally quantify. Therefore, the overall decay rate is given by

$$\kappa = \kappa_{in} + \tilde{\kappa}, \quad (2.15)$$

where κ_{in} is the input-coupler of the cavity (i.e., the decay channel we can measure), and $\tilde{\kappa}$ is a collection of all other loss mechanisms that we are unable to detect. Assume a coherent laser field with a fixed center frequency of ω_0 and a complex amplitude ϵ that has been correctly re-scaled and is used to drive an optical cavity. This amplitude and the input power P_{in} are connected by

$$|\epsilon| = \sqrt{\frac{P_{in}}{\hbar\omega_0}}, \quad (2.16)$$

Here square root term describes the driving laser photon flux is considered. The equation of motion for the mean interactivity field α_c followed.

$$\dot{\alpha}_c = -(\iota\omega_c + \frac{\kappa}{2})\alpha_c + \sqrt{\kappa_{in}}\epsilon e^{-\iota\omega_0 t}, \quad (2.17)$$

At optical frequencies, we can get rid of the trivial evolution by introducing

$$\tilde{\alpha}_c(t) = \alpha_c(t)e^{\iota\omega_0 t}, \quad (2.18)$$

$\tilde{\alpha}_c$ will be assumed a constant steady state amplitude $\tilde{\alpha}_c^{ss}$ after a transient period.

$$\tilde{\alpha}_c^{ss} = \frac{\sqrt{\kappa_{in}}\epsilon}{l\Delta_0 - \frac{\kappa}{2}}, \quad (2.19)$$

with the de-tuning Δ_0 of the laser with respect to the cavity resonance frequency

$$\Delta_0 = \omega_0 - \omega_c, \quad (2.20)$$

We can distinguish between the input coupling rate κ_{in} and the overall decay rate κ , which causes a decrease in the interaction photon number with rising losses $\tilde{\kappa}$. We can obtain the linear response function for the cavity's susceptibility $\chi(\omega_0)$ by taking the Fourier transform of equation (2.33). The response of the system for a constant input at frequency ω_0 can be obtained with the value of $\chi(\omega_0)$ and is given by Lorentzian

$$\chi(\omega) = \frac{\sqrt{\kappa_{in}}}{\frac{\kappa}{2} - l(\omega - \omega_c)}, \quad (2.21)$$

The amplitude and phase responses of the intracavity field are given by its modulus and argument, respectively. The intracavity field in quantum mechanics can be expressed as a damped harmonic oscillator. To introduce the related dimensionless quadrature operators, the creation and annihilation operators c_c^\dagger , and c_c , respectively[53].

$$x_c = \frac{c_c + c_c^\dagger}{\sqrt{2}}, \quad (2.22)$$

$$p_c = \frac{c_c - c_c^\dagger}{\sqrt{2}l}, \quad (2.23)$$

x_c is referred to as the amplitude quadrature, and p_c is referred to as the phase quadrature of the electromagnetic field. the interaction between the optical and mechanical modes usually assumes the form of dispersive coupling. This implies that changes in the mechanical oscillator's position result in a shift in the cavity's resonance frequency. This interaction is physically mediated by

radiation pressure, involving either momentum transfer through reflection (as seen in Fabry–Pérot setups and microtoroids) or gradient forces (as observed in setups with a membrane placed in the middle).

2.4 The Hamiltonian

A single mechanical mode interacts with a single optical mode. Expanding this concept to encompass scenarios with multiple modes is quite straightforward. The derivation of the Hamiltonian governing the interaction between a cavity and mechanical motion. Our starting point is the Hamiltonian that describes two harmonic oscillators operating independently without any coupling (uncoupled) between them.

$$H_0 = \hbar\omega_m C_m^\dagger C_m + \hbar\omega_c C_c^\dagger C_c, \quad (2.24)$$

The ω_m represents the resonance frequency of the mechanical motion, and ω_c stands for the resonance frequency of the optical cavity (also known as the nominal cavity frequency). We use $[c_i, c_j^\dagger]$ to denote the commutation relation between operators c_i and c_j^\dagger . The optical resonance frequency ω_c is determined by the time taken for photons to complete a round trip within the cavity. This, in turn, depends on the effective cavity length denoted as L . In other words, $\omega_c/2\pi = 2C/L$, where c is the speed of light. When the mirror undergoes displacement, it causes a shift in the resonance frequency. Consequently, this alteration impacts the energy contained within the cavity mode. Notably, for relatively small displacements $X_m/L \ll 1$, this effect becomes significant.

$$\omega_c(X_m) = \omega_c + \frac{\partial\omega_c}{\partial X_m} X_m + O(X_m)^2, \quad (2.25)$$

The Hamiltonian for the optomechanical system is considered. By taking into account first-order effects in X_m , the relationship $X_m X_0 (C_m + C_m^\dagger) = \sqrt{2} X_0 X_m$ is utilized to derive the Hamiltonian that governs the optomechanical system.

$$H_{nl} = \hbar\omega_m C_m^\dagger C_m + \hbar\omega_c C_c^\dagger C_c + \hbar g_0 x_m C_c^\dagger C_c, \quad (2.26)$$

The single-photon optomechanical coupling strength.

$$g_0 = \sqrt{2}x_0 \frac{\partial\omega_c}{\partial X_m}, \quad (2.27)$$

The connection between the mechanical oscillator and a single photon within the cavity is quantified by this equation. In the Fabry–Pérot scenario, $g_0 = \sqrt{2}X_0\omega_c/L$, and the inverse of L are relevant. It's noteworthy that, as per these definitions, a positive value for the displacement $X_m > 0$ results in an augmentation of cavity energy, signifying a reduction in the cavity length.

$$H_{drive} = -i\hbar[E^*(t)e^{i\omega_0 t}C_c - E(t)e^{-i\omega_0 t}C_c^\dagger], \quad (2.28)$$

The radiation-pressure interaction displays nonlinearity with respect to the amplitudes c_i, c_i^\dagger , and it varies according to the photon number inside the cavity. However, due to the typically small value of g_0 in many current optomechanical systems, observing pronounced nonlinear dynamics and optomechanical effects at the single-photon level can be challenging. To amplify the influence of radiation pressure, one strategy involves employing a powerful laser beam to drive the optomechanical cavity. This laser beam carries a substantial coherent amplitude $\epsilon(t)$ that varies with time. Such a driving force, centered at the frequency ω_0 , can be incorporated through the addition of an extra driving term.

$$H_{nl} = \frac{1}{2}\hbar\omega_m(x_m^2 + p_m^2) - \hbar\Delta_0 C_c^\dagger C_c + \hbar g_0 x_m C_c^\dagger C_c - i\hbar[E^*(t)C_c - E(t)C_c^\dagger], \quad (2.29)$$

For a strong laser drive the optomechanical Hamiltonian given in above equation (2.31) can be approximation.

$$H_{lin} = \hbar\omega_m C_m^\dagger C_m - \hbar\Delta_c C_c^\dagger C_c + \hbar \frac{g_0 \alpha_c}{\sqrt{2}} (C_m + C^\dagger)(C_c + C^\dagger), \quad (2.30)$$

An effective detuning, Δ_c , has been introduced, which undergoes a shift from Δ_0 owing to the altered equilibrium position of the mirror. The coupling strength $g = g_0\alpha_c/\sqrt{2}$ of the linear interaction is enhanced by the inclusion of the term α_c . In the current context, α_c denotes the square root of the photon number within the cavity. When a high-finesse cavity or a robust laser drive is dealt with, a considerable average photon count within the cavity can be observed. Consequently, the strength of interaction can undergo a significant increase by several orders of magnitude.

$$H_{bs} = \hbar g(C_m C_c^\dagger + C_m C_c), \quad (2.31)$$

The detuning, Δ_c , allows us to recognize various interaction modes arising from the linearized radiation pressure Hamiltonian. One such interaction mode is referred to as the beam-splitter (BS) Hamiltonian.

$$H_{tms} = \hbar g(C_m C_c + C_m^\dagger C_c^\dagger), \quad (2.32)$$

The above equation becomes resonant when $\Delta_c = -\omega_m$ is matched, The coherent transfer of energy between the mechanical oscillator and the cavity mode is observed. This aspect cooling down the mechanical motion using sideband cooling techniques and can also be harnessed to achieve a state exchange between the two modes. This specific interaction is known as the two-mode squeezing (TMS) interaction.

2.5 Quantum Langevin Equations

1. Heisenberg Uncertainty Principle:

The Heisenberg uncertainty principle is a fundamental concept in quantum mechanics that states that certain pairs of physical properties, such as position and momentum, cannot be precisely measured simultaneously. The more accurately you measure one property, the less accurately you can measure the other. This intrinsic uncertainty is a fundamental aspect of quantum mechanics.

2. Langevin Equation:

The Langevin equation is a stochastic differential equation commonly used to describe the motion of particles in a fluctuating environment. It accounts for both deterministic forces (such as applied forces) and random forces (representing the influence of the surrounding environment). The Langevin equation is often used in classical mechanics to model the behavior of particles undergoing Brownian motion.

3. Heisenberg-Langevin Approach:

The Heisenberg-Langevin approach extends the ideas of the Langevin equation to the context of quantum mechanics. It considers the effects of noise and fluctuations on quantum observables, similar to how the Langevin equation describes the motion of classical particles in a noisy environment.

The Heisenberg-Langevin approach is particularly useful for understanding how quantum systems respond to external influences and fluctuations. It is often applied in fields such as quantum optics, quantum electronics, and quantum information theory, where quantum systems are frequently subjected to environmental noise that can affect their behavior.

2.6 Quantum Fluctuations and Noise in the Heisenberg-Langevin Framework

The optical cavity is driven by a strong laser field of frequency ω_l and a weak probe field of frequency ω_p . The mechanical resonators, MR_1 and MR_2 , are subjected to external driving fields with amplitudes ϵ_1 and ϵ_2 , respectively.

Δ_c : This term represents the detuning of the cavity field from the laser frequency.

κ : The cavity decay rate, which quantifies the rate at which energy or information is lost from the optical cavity.

G_0 : The single-photon optomechanical coupling strength that governs the interaction between the cavity field and the mechanical resonators.

b_1^\dagger and b_1 : Creation and annihilation operators for the mechanical mode MR_1 .

$\sqrt{2\kappa}c_{in}(t)$: Represents the interaction of the cavity with an external quantum input field $c_{in}(t)$, with coupling strength determined by κ .

$$\dot{c} = - \left(i\Delta_c + \frac{\kappa}{2} \right) c + iG_0 \left(b_1^\dagger + b_1 \right) c + \epsilon_l + \epsilon_p e^{-i\delta t} + \sqrt{2\kappa} c_{\text{in}}(t), \quad (2.33)$$

ω_1 : The resonance frequency of the mechanical resonator MR_1 .

ω_2 : The resonance frequency of the mechanical resonator MR_2 .

ϵ_1 : Amplitude of the external driving field applied to MR_1 .

ϵ_2 : Amplitude of the external driving field applied to MR_2 .

γ_1 : The mechanical damping rate of MR_1 , representing energy dissipation.

γ_2 : The mechanical damping rate of MR_2 , representing energy dissipation.

$\sqrt{2\gamma_1}\zeta_1$: The stochastic Brownian noise operator $\zeta_1(t)$ associated with MR_1 , scaled by the damping rate γ_1 .

$\sqrt{2\gamma_2}\zeta_2$: The stochastic Brownian noise operator $\zeta_2(t)$ associated with MR_2 , scaled by the damping rate γ_2 . The dynamics of the coupled optomechanical system, consisting of a single-mode optical cavity and two mechanical resonators (MR_1 and MR_2), can be described using the Heisenberg-Langevin formalism. In this approach, the time evolution of the system operators accounts for both the coherent interactions and the effects of dissipation and quantum noise.

The cavity field operator c evolves according to

$$\dot{c} = - \left(i\Delta_c + \frac{\kappa}{2} \right) c + iG_0 \left(b_1^\dagger + b_1 \right) c + \epsilon_l + \epsilon_p e^{-i\delta t} + \sqrt{2\kappa} c_{\text{in}}(t), \quad (2.34)$$

where Δ_c is the detuning between the cavity resonance and the driving laser, κ is the cavity decay rate, G_0 is the single-photon optomechanical coupling, and $c_{\text{in}}(t)$ represents the input quantum noise of the optical field.

The mechanical resonators are described by the operators b_1 and b_2 , whose dynamics are governed by

$$\dot{b}_1 = - \left(i\omega_1 + \frac{\gamma_1}{2} \right) b_1 + iG_0 c^\dagger c - iG_c b_2 + \epsilon_1 e^{-i\delta t - i\phi_1} + \sqrt{2\gamma_1} \xi_1(t), \quad (2.35)$$

$$\dot{b}_2 = - \left(i\omega_2 + \frac{\gamma_2}{2} \right) b_2 - iG_c b_1 + \epsilon_2 e^{-i\delta t - i\phi_2} + \sqrt{2\gamma_2} \xi_2(t), \quad (2.36)$$

where ω_1 and ω_2 are the mechanical resonance frequencies, γ_1 and γ_2 are the

mechanical damping rates, G_c is the inter-resonator coupling strength, ϵ_1 and ϵ_2 are the amplitudes of the external driving fields, ϕ_1 and ϕ_2 are their respective phases, and $\zeta_1(t)$ and $\zeta_2(t)$ are stochastic Brownian noise operators representing coupling to thermal reservoirs.

These equations encapsulate the key physical processes:

- **Coherent dynamics:** The terms proportional to G_0 and G_c describe radiation pressure interactions and inter-resonator coupling, respectively.
- **Dissipation:** The decay terms $\kappa/2$ and $\gamma_{1,2}/2$ account for the energy loss due to cavity leakage and mechanical damping.
- **External driving:** The coherent drives ϵ_l , ϵ_p , ϵ_1 , and ϵ_2 inject energy into the system.
- **Quantum noise:** The operators $c_{in}(t)$ and $\zeta_{1,2}(t)$ model the influence of the environment, introducing fluctuations consistent with the fluctuation-dissipation theorem.

Together, the Heisenberg-Langevin equations provide a complete description of the open quantum dynamics of the coupled cavity-mechanical system, capturing both coherent evolution and stochastic effects due to environmental interactions.

\hat{c}_{in} signifies the input vacuum noise linked to the cavity field, featuring a zero mean value. Meanwhile, the expressions $\zeta_1(t)$ and $\zeta_2(t)$ stand for Brownian noise operators related to the damping of MR1 and MR2 respectively. The symbols κ and γ_i ($i = 1, 2$) represent decay terms connected to the cavity and MRi ($i = 1, 2$) correspondingly. Employing the mean field approximation, the noise term mean values are averaged to zero, considering dissipation and fluctuation components. This process leads us to the equations.

$$\langle \dot{c} \rangle = -(\imath\Delta_c + \frac{\kappa}{2})\langle c \rangle + \imath G_0(\langle b_1^\dagger \rangle + \langle b_1 \rangle)\langle c \rangle + \epsilon_l + \epsilon_p e^{-\imath\delta t} + \sqrt{2\kappa}c_{in}(t), \quad (2.37)$$

$$\langle \dot{b}_1 \rangle = -(\iota\omega_1 + \frac{\gamma_1}{2})\langle b_1 \rangle + \iota G_0 \langle c^\dagger \rangle \langle c \rangle - \iota G_c \langle b \rangle_2 + \epsilon_1 e^{-\iota\delta t - \iota\phi_1} + \sqrt{2\kappa}\zeta_1(t), \quad (2.38)$$

$$\langle \dot{b}_2 \rangle = -(\iota\omega_2 + \frac{\gamma_2}{2})\langle b_2 \rangle - \iota G_c \langle b_1 \rangle + \epsilon_2 e^{-\iota\delta t - \iota\phi_2} + \sqrt{2\gamma_2}\zeta_2(t), \quad (2.39)$$

With these three equations we obtain the steady-state solutions. we see the effective detuning is $\Delta = \Delta_c - G_0 q_{1s}$, Also $\wp_p \ll \wp_l$, , only consider strong laser power

$$c_s = \frac{\epsilon_l + \epsilon_p}{\iota\Delta + \frac{\kappa}{2}}, \quad (2.40)$$

$$b_{1s} = \frac{\iota G_0 |c_s|^2 - \iota G_c b_{2s} + \epsilon_1 e^{-\iota\phi_1}}{\iota\omega_1 + \frac{\gamma_1}{2}}, \quad (2.41)$$

$$b_{2s} = \frac{-\iota G_c b_{1s} + \epsilon_2 e^{-\iota\phi_2}}{\iota\omega_2 + \frac{\gamma_2}{2}}. \quad (2.42)$$

2.7 The Model

We consider a high-Q Fabry-Perot cavity of length L. According to Figure 1, the cavity is made up of a fixed mirror and a movable nano-mechanical resonator MR1, with a driving field and a probe field, as shown in Fig. 4.1 The total Hamiltonian of the given system is

The equation you've provided represents the total Hamiltonian \hat{H} of a physical system as the sum of three distinct components: \hat{H}_{mc} , \hat{H}_{dr} and \hat{H}_{int} . In quantum mechanics, the Hamiltonian operator represents the total energy of a system and governs its time evolution. Let's see the equation and its components:

2.8 Total Hamiltonian of the System

We examine a high-Q Fabry-Perot cavity characterized by its length, denoted as L . This cavity comprises a stationary mirror MR_{fixed} and a movable nano-mechanical resonator MR_1 , subject to a driving field ϵ_l and a probe field ϵ_p . External modulating fields drive mirrors MR_1 and MR_2 individually. Furthermore, MR_1 is linked to the cavity field through the radiation pressure force, and it connects to another movable mirror MR_2 via an adjustable electrostatic Coulomb coupling force. The oscillation frequency of MR_1 is ω_1 , and that of MR_2 is ω_2 . The strength of Coulomb coupling is regulated through bias voltages: $+V_1$ for MR_1 and $-V_2$ for MR_2 . This implies that, alongside the opto-mechanical coupling, the system includes a modifiable Coulomb coupling intensity.

$$\hat{H} = \hat{H}_{mc} + \hat{H}_{dr} + \hat{H}_{int}. \quad (2.43)$$

2.9 Mirror and Field Hamiltonian

In the uncoupled scenario, denoted by H_{mc} , within a rotating reference frame at frequency, the mirror and field Hamiltonian is observed. The detuning of the cavity field frequency is indicated by $\Delta_c = \omega_c - \omega_l$. The initial component embodies the single-mode of the cavity field, characterized by frequency ω_c and the annihilation (or creation) operator $\hat{c}(\hat{c}^\dagger)$. The following two terms correspond to the independent Hamiltonian of the movable mirrors, MR_i , each having mass m_i and oscillating at frequency ω_i , where $i = 1; 2$. The operators, q_i , and p_i , symbolize position and momentum, respectively.

$$\hat{H}_{mc} = \hbar\Delta_c\hat{c}^\dagger\hat{c} + \left[\frac{\hat{p}_1^2}{2m_1} + \frac{1}{2}m_1\omega_1^2\hat{q}_1^2 \right] + \left[\frac{\hat{p}_2^2}{2m_2} + \frac{1}{2}m_2\omega_2^2\hat{q}_2^2 \right]. \quad (2.44)$$

Figure 2.3: The schematic of the Nano-Electro-Opto-Mechanical system. The mechanical resonator MR_1 is connected to the cavity field via optomechanical coupling represented by g_0 , and the second mechanical resonator MR_2 through the strength of Coulomb coupling, g_c . An input laser field with amplitude ϵ_l and a probe field with amplitude ϵ_p are introduced into the cavity through the fixed mirror. Furthermore, MR_1 is influenced by the biased voltage $+V_1$, while MR_2 is influenced by the biased voltage $-V_2$. In this context, L signifies the cavity's length, ϵ_1 and ϵ_2 refer to the external driving fields on MR_1 and MR_2 respectively, ϵ_{out} pertains to the output probe field, and γ_1 and γ_2 denote the mirror decay rates.

2.10 Driving Field Hamiltonian

\hat{H}_{dr} combine Hamiltonian of various components, including the strong laser field with amplitude ϵ_l , the weak probe field with amplitude ϵ_p and the external driving fields ϵ_1 and ϵ_2 . Here, $\delta_c = \omega_p - \omega_l$ symbolizes the detuning frequency of the probe field from the laser frequency ω_l . The initial two terms represent the classical light fields (pump and probe) at frequencies ω_l and ω_p respectively. The strong laser power \wp_l and the probe field power \wp_l correspond to ω_l and ω_p through relations ϵ_l and ϵ_p , respectively. The ultimate term depicts the Hamiltonian of external modulation applied to MR_1

and MR2, where ϵ_j ($j = 1; 2$) denotes amplitude and phase. The symbols b_j and b_j^\dagger correspond to the phonon annihilation and creation operators of MR1 and MR2 respectively. Minor oscillations of the MRs from their mean positions can be defined as $q_j = \sqrt{\frac{\hbar}{2m_j\omega_j}}(b_j + b_j^\dagger)$. Similarly, the oscillations in mirror momenta can be described using the relation $\hat{q}_j = p_j/m_j$. The third Hamiltonian term, H_{int} , represents the coupling between the cavity field and MR1 through opto-mechanics, along with the Coulomb coupling linking MR1 and MR2. This is expressed as:

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{H}_{dr} = & i\hbar\epsilon_l (\hat{c}^\dagger - \hat{c}) \\ & + i\hbar (\epsilon_p e^{-i\delta t} \hat{c}^\dagger - \epsilon_p^* e^{i\delta t} \hat{c}) \\ & + i\hbar \sum_{j=1}^2 (\epsilon_j \hat{q}_j e^{-i\delta t + i\Phi_j} - \epsilon_j \hat{q}_j^\dagger e^{i\delta t - i\phi_j}). \end{aligned} \quad (2.45)$$

2.11 Interaction Hamiltonian

The component signifies the interaction between MR1 and the cavity field due to opto-mechanical coupling. The following element represents the Coulomb-based coupling involving the moving mirrors. Specifically, the optomechanical coupling strength, denoted as $g_0 = (\frac{\omega_c}{L} \sqrt{\frac{\hbar}{2m_1\omega_1}})$, is calculated as $g_0 = \omega_c$, while the Coulomb coupling strength is represented as $g_c = \frac{\kappa_c C_1 V_1 C_2 V_2}{\hbar r_0^3}$. The stable distance between the two resonators is denoted as r_0 . In terms of phonon annihilation (or creation) operators, it can be expressed as $b_j(b_j^\dagger)$. The total Hamiltonian of the system can be divided into the free evolution of the cavity and mechanical modes, and their interactions.

The free Hamiltonian is given by

$$\hat{H}_{mc} = -\hbar\Delta \hat{c}^\dagger \hat{c} + \hbar\omega_1 b_1^\dagger b_1 + \hbar\omega_2 b_2^\dagger b_2, \quad (2.46)$$

where \hat{c} (\hat{c}^\dagger) is the annihilation (creation) operator for the cavity mode, $\Delta = \omega_l - \omega_c$ is the detuning of the driving laser from the cavity resonance, and b_1, b_2 are the annihilation operators of the mechanical resonators with frequencies ω_1

and ω_2 , respectively. The first term represents the cavity energy in the rotating frame, while the second and third terms describe the free harmonic motion of the mechanical resonators.

The interaction Hamiltonian is expressed as

$$\hat{H}_{int} = -\hbar g_0 \hat{c}^\dagger \hat{c} \hat{q}_1 + \hbar g_c \hat{q}_1 \hat{q}_2, \quad (2.47)$$

where g_0 is the single-photon optomechanical coupling between the cavity field and MR_1 , g_c is the Coulomb or elastic coupling strength between the two mechanical resonators, and \hat{q}_1, \hat{q}_2 are the dimensionless position operators of MR_1 and MR_2 . The first term accounts for the radiation-pressure interaction, while the second term models the direct coupling between the mechanical resonators, enabling coherent energy exchange.

Together, \hat{H}_{mc} and \hat{H}_{int} provide a complete description of the coherent dynamics of the hybrid optomechanical system, forming the basis for studying optomechanical effects, normal-mode splitting, and cavity-mediated mechanical correlations.

The detuning frequency of the probe field from the laser frequency is denoted as $\delta_c = \omega_p - \omega_l$. The initial two terms encompass the classical optical fields (pump and probe) characterized by frequencies ω_1 and ω_2 respectively. The relationship between the strong laser power \wp_l and the probe field power is expressed through the variables $\epsilon_l = \sqrt{\frac{2\kappa\wp_l}{\hbar\omega_l}}$ and $\epsilon_p = \sqrt{\frac{2\kappa\wp_l}{\hbar\omega_p}}$ respectively.

$$\hat{H}_{int} = -\hbar G_0 \hat{c}^\dagger \hat{c} (b_1 + b_1^\dagger) + \hbar G_c (b_1^\dagger b_2 + b_1 b_2^\dagger). \quad (2.48)$$

The optomechanical coupling strengths in the system are characterized by the parameters G_0 , which quantify the interaction between the optical field and the mechanical modes. For a single mechanical oscillator of mass m_1 and frequency ω_1 , the coupling is given by

$$G_0 = g_0 \sqrt{\frac{\hbar}{2m_1\omega_1}}, \quad (2.49)$$

where g_0 represents the single-photon optomechanical coupling rate. In the

case of two coupled mechanical modes with masses m_1 and m_2 and frequencies ω_1 and ω_2 , the effective coupling is expressed as

$$G_0 = g_c \sqrt{\frac{1}{2m_1 m_2 \omega_1 \omega_2}}, \quad (2.50)$$

where g_c denotes the inter-mode coupling rate. These expressions show that the coupling strength depends not only on the intrinsic interaction rates (g_0 or g_c) but also on the mechanical properties of the oscillators, specifically their masses and frequencies. This scaling ensures that lighter or higher-frequency oscillators generally exhibit stronger quantum optomechanical interactions.

Chapter 3

Optical Bi- Stability Results

The optical bistability has been observed experimentally in micro cavities[48]. In our work the bistability behaviour is the effect of non linearity that comes from the strength of optomechanical coupling G_0 and the strength of coulomb coupling G_c . The solution of equation (3.6) provides us with steady state values of cavity photon number and is given below

$$|\epsilon_l + \epsilon_p|^2 = |c_s|^2 \left[\frac{\kappa^2}{4} + (\Delta_c - G_0(b_{1s}^* + b_{1s}))^2 \right]. \quad (3.1)$$

Here $|c_s|^2 = c_s c_s^*$. The occurrence of bistable behavior in the system can be seen through this equation. In equation (3.8), if we take $G_0 = 0$ then the bistability in photon number will vanishes. We can obtain a third order polynomial of the steady state intracavity photon numbers by rearranging the equation (3.8) as below

$$a_1 x^3 + a_2 x^2 + a_3 x + a_4 = 0. \quad (3.2)$$

Where

$$x = |c_s|^2. \quad (3.3)$$

$$a_1 = G_0^2 a_1^2, \quad (3.4)$$

$$a_2 = 2\alpha_1(\Gamma + \Delta_c G_0), \quad (3.5)$$

$$a_3 = \left(\frac{\kappa^2}{4} + \Delta_c^2 + G_0\Gamma(G_0\Gamma + 2\Delta_c) \right), \quad (3.6)$$

$$a_4 = -|\epsilon_l + \epsilon_p|^2, \quad (3.7)$$

Here, $\alpha_1 = \beta_1 + \beta_1^*$, $\Gamma = \alpha_2\epsilon_2 + \alpha_3\epsilon_1$, $\alpha_2 = \beta_2e^{-i\phi_2} + \beta_2^*e^{i\phi_2}$, $\alpha_3 = \beta_3e^{i\phi_1} + \beta_3^*e^{-i\phi_1}$, $\beta_1 = \frac{i(\omega_2 + \gamma_2/2)G_0}{(i\omega_1 + \gamma_1/2)(i\omega_2/2) + G_c^2}$, $\beta_2 = -\frac{G_c}{G_0} \frac{\beta_1}{(i\omega_2 + \gamma_2/2)}$ and $\beta_3 = \frac{-i\beta_1}{G_0}$. This equation has three roots, two of which correspond to stable regimes of the steady state photon number and the third to an unstable regime. with inflection and critical points, i.e. $y_c = \frac{-b \pm \sqrt{b^2 - 3ac}}{3a}$ and $y_{inf} = -b/3a$. The solutions of the cubic polynomial equation $ay^3 + by^2 + cy + d = 0$ provides the branches of the bi-stable curve. Using the solutions for y_c and y_{inf} , we can write the critical and inflection points of the Equation (5.1) as,

$$x_{c\pm} = \frac{-a_2/a_1 \pm \sqrt{(a_2/a_1)^2 - 3a_3/a_1}}{3}, \quad x_{inf} = -a_2/3a_1, \quad (3.8)$$

where x_{c+} and x_{c-} are critical points of upper and lower stable limbs of the bistable curve respectively, while x_{inf} is the inflection point of the curve. The range of the bistability window is determined by these critical points and at these points the driving laser field power \wp_l , has a corresponding window also. We think our new system works with small differences between vibration frequencies, and these small differences can change when the laser light is stronger. So, when we make the laser light stronger, the number of photons also goes up. So, when the laser is really strong within a specific range, the number of photons stays in two different states. When we make the laser even stronger, the light's change in frequency comes close to a specific value, which we call "critical detuning." At this critical point, the two states of photon number start to appear. This special frequency value decides when the two states happen in the system.

$$\Delta_c = \sqrt{3}\kappa \quad (3.9)$$

We want to explore how to control when light and mirrors switch between two states in the new nanosystem we made (NEOMS). We use some numbers from recent experiments [31, 32]. The cavity inside NEOMS has a length of $L = 25$ cm, and $r_0 = 2$ mm. To keep things simple, we use two identical mechanical mirrors (MRs) with masses $m_1 = m_2 = 145$ ng each. They vibrate at around an oscillation frequency $\omega_1 = \omega_2 = 2\pi \times 947$ kHz and decay rates $\gamma_1(\gamma_2) = 140$ kHz. The cavity where decay rates is $\kappa = 2\pi \times 215$ kHz. We figure out the light's frequency using its speed and the wavelength of the light, which is 1064 nm. We pick some numbers for calculations, and the pump light's power is 9 mW. Since the mechanical part's frequency is higher than the light's fading speed, everything happens in a certain way.

3.1 Intra-Cavity Photon Number

The particles of light, that are present within a confined space called a cavity. This cavity is typically designed to trap and contain light. The concept is important in various fields like quantum optics and laser physics. The photon number within the cavity can vary based on factors such as the input of light, the characteristics of the cavity, and interactions with surrounding materials. Researchers often study the behavior of intra-cavity photon numbers to understand how light behaves in confined environments and how it interacts with matter. By controlling and manipulating the intra-cavity photon number, scientists can achieve effects like optical amplification, lasing, and quantum entanglement. This concept finds applications in technologies ranging from lasers and optical communication systems to quantum computing and precision measurement devices.

We're looking at how the number of steady photons changes when we change the laser power \wp_1 . There are specific points on the graph: critical points are where the curve has lower and higher stable sections, and inflection points P and Q show where the curve becomes unstable. When we start with a weak laser and slowly make it stronger, the photon intensity first follows the lower stable part S_1 of the curve, and then suddenly jumps to the upper stable part S_2 when the laser power reaches a certain value. if the driving laser

power are increase to 7.6mW. The upper stable part extends until a specific point. There's a dashed blue line that's unstable and goes between points P and Q. The unstable line slopes downward, but we can't really see it in real experiments. If we start with a strong laser and gradually weaken it, the photon number first follows the upper stable part, then jumps to the lower stable part at a different critical points x_{c+} , x_{c-} , and continues to decrease from there.

We present a comprehensive examination of controllable bistability, predominantly affected by factors like coupling frequencies and external modulation field strength. The intracavity photon count vs. laser power shows an S-shaped bistability curve at different levels of optomechanical coupling, with overlapping bifurcation curves for various coupling frequencies. Increasing optomechanical coupling strength G_0 enhances mechanical back-action, augmenting radiation pressure force and leading to photon dispersion within the cavity.

Figure 3.1: The average intracavity photon number $|C_s|^2$, in relation to the driving laser power, ϕ_1 . These results are obtained using specific system parameters for this scenario, including $m_1 = m_2 = 145$ ng and $\omega_1 = \omega_2 = 947$ kHz, $\epsilon = \epsilon = 0$, and $G_0 = 2\pi \times 215$ kHz.

The bifurcation curve initially traces the upper stable branch at a lower

coupling regime, specifically at $G_0/2\pi = 6kHz$ (depicted by the solid black line). As the optomechanical coupling frequency is further increased, the upper stable path follows the lower stable path. This transition occurs at $G_0/2\pi = 7kHz$ (represented by the dashed black curve). Alongside the alteration in photon counts, enhancing the optomechanical coupling frequency also narrows the bistable curve. When G_0 , the optomechanical coupling strength G_0 , is raised, the third lower stable path succeeds the second lower stable path, and vice versa.

3.2 Effect of external mechanical driving fields on optical bistability

The steady-state photon number's bistable curve without any external mechanical driving forces is represented as ϵ_1 and ϵ_2 . We introduce external mechanical pumps to activate micro-resonators MR_1 and MR_2 , investigating the sudden alterations in system bistability. Consequently, we apply mechanical pumps (acoustic stimulants) $\epsilon_j = \epsilon_j e^{-i\phi_j}$ ($j = 1; 2$) to the mechanical resonators MRs, analyzing their impact on the intracavity photon count, denoted as $|C_s|^2$.

Applying a mechanical pump field to MR_1 results in intriguing phase-sensitive optical phenomena in the NEOMS. By maintaining the constant amplitude ϵ and varying the phase angle ϕ , altering the angle from $\pi/4$ to π leads to amplified steady-state intracavity photon intensity,

An intriguing observation appears in the bistability plot, where the curves intersect at the same point and the upper stable branches follow one another, as do the lower stable paths. Conversely, when driving the second mechanical resonator MR_2 , maintaining the constant amplitude ϵ_2 and altering the phase angle brings forth slight modifications in the upper stable branch of the curve. The transition between paths is evident as the blue solid, blue dashed, and black long-dashed curves shift.

Interestingly, this transition doesn't mirror in the lower stable paths, which remain independent of the phase angle. This behavior is attributed to the fact that the external modulating field only alters the effective Coulomb coupling

CHAPTER 3. OPTICAL BI- STABILITY RESULTS

strength between the mirrors, without directly affecting the radiation pressure force.

By selectively driving mechanical resonators MR_1 and MR_2 while maintaining constant phase angles and varying amplitude, similar behaviors of the bistable curve can be observed. This demonstrates the complex interplay between external modulation, phase angles, and amplitude in shaping the optical responses of the system.

Chapter 4

Bose-Einstein Condensate in Nano-Electro-Optomechanics

4.1 Basic Theory and System Model

Bose-Einstein condensation (BEC) is a quantum phenomenon in which a macroscopic number of bosonic atoms occupy the same quantum state, leading to the emergence of a coherent matter wave. The concept was theoretically predicted by Satyendra Nath Bose and Albert Einstein in 1924. BEC is typically realized by cooling samples of bosons to temperatures near absolute zero using techniques such as laser cooling [54], evaporative cooling [55], and magneto-optical trapping [56].

The first experimental observation of a pure Bose-Einstein condensate was achieved in Rubidium-87 by Eric Cornell, Carl Wieman, and their collaborators in June 1995 [57], using a combination of laser cooling and magnetic-evaporative cooling [58]. Shortly thereafter, Wolfgang Ketterle independently realized BEC in Sodium-23 at MIT [59]. BEC in Lithium atoms was later achieved by Randall Hulet at Rice University. Since then, numerous research groups have explored BEC formation using optical trapping techniques [60].

Bose-Einstein condensates provide an ideal platform for studying quantum optical phenomena, such as Electromagnetically Induced Transparency (EIT) [61] and slow light [62]. The coherent nature of BECs makes them par-

ticularly suitable for experiments in optical information processing, quantum memory, and light-matter interaction.

4.1.1 System Model

To investigate the dynamics of a Bose-Einstein condensate (BEC) in a nano-electro-opto-mechanical system (NEOMS), we consider a setup where a BEC is trapped inside a high-Q optical cavity, as illustrated in Figure 4.1.

Figure 4.1: **Schematic of the NEOMS with a trapped BEC:** The movable mirror MR_1 interacts with the cavity field via radiation-pressure optomechanical coupling, while the cavity field also couples to the two-level atoms of the BEC with atomic coupling strength g . The mechanical resonators MR_1 and MR_2 are coupled through a tunable Coulomb interaction g_c , with MR_1 charged by a bias voltage V_1 and MR_2 by $-V_2$. The cavity mode is driven through the fixed mirror by a strong pump laser of amplitude ϵ_1 and a weak probe field of amplitude ϵ_p . L denotes the cavity length, ϵ_1 and ϵ_2 are external driving fields applied to MR_1 and MR_2 , respectively, and r_0 is the equilibrium distance between the two mechanical resonators.

In this system, MR_1 mediates the interaction between the cavity field and the BEC, while also coupling mechanically to MR_2 through the Coulomb inter-

CHAPTER 4. BOSE-EINSTEIN CONDENSATE IN NANO-ELECTRO-OPTOMECHANICS

action. The optical cavity is driven by both a strong pump and a weak probe, enabling the study of optomechanically induced transparency, coherent dynamics, and light-matter interactions within the BEC. External driving fields ϵ_1 and ϵ_2 allow for additional control of the mechanical resonators, and the bias voltages V_1 and $-V_2$ provide tunability of the Coulomb coupling strength. The equilibrium distance r_0 determines the static separation between the two movable resonators, which plays a crucial role in the overall system dynamics.

4.1.2 Mathematical Treatment

In the considered NEOMS, the atomic density of the Bose-Einstein condensate is sufficiently high that two-body atom-atom interactions cannot be neglected. Additionally, on-site kinetic energy and tunneling (hopping) of atoms between lattice sites are significant. Therefore, the Bose-Hubbard model (BHM) [63] is employed to describe the condensate dynamics within the optical cavity.

Starting from the microscopic second-quantized Hamiltonian, the system is described by

$$H = \int dx \psi^\dagger(x) \left[-\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \nabla^2 + V(x) \right] \psi(x) + \frac{\lambda}{2} \int d^3x \psi^\dagger(x) \psi^\dagger(x) \psi(x) \psi(x), \quad (4.1)$$

where $\psi(x)$ ($\psi^\dagger(x)$) are the bosonic field annihilation (creation) operators, m is the atomic mass, and $\lambda = \frac{4\pi a_s \hbar^2}{m}$ is the effective two-body interaction strength determined by the s-wave scattering length a_s . The external potential experienced by the atoms is given by

$$V(x) = U_0 c^\dagger c \cos^2(kx), \quad (4.2)$$

where k is the wave number of the cavity mode, and $U_0 = \frac{g^2}{\Delta_a}$ represents the optical lattice depth induced by the cavity field, with g as the atom-light coupling strength and Δ_a the detuning between the atomic transition and cavity mode.

To map the continuous field Hamiltonian onto a lattice description, the atomic field operator is expanded in terms of localized Wannier functions $\omega_n(x -$

x_i) as

$$\psi(x) = \sum_{i,n} \omega_n(x - x_i) b_i, \quad (4.3)$$

where b_i is the annihilation operator for a boson at site i and band n . This formulation allows the derivation of the Bose-Hubbard Hamiltonian, capturing both the on-site interactions and the tunneling between lattice sites induced by the cavity field.

4.1.3 Optomechanical Bose-Hubbard Hamiltonian

By considering the nearest-neighbor approximation [64], the dynamics of a Bose-Einstein condensate (BEC) within a nano-electro-optomechanical system (NEOMS) can be described using the optomechanical Bose-Hubbard Hamiltonian (OMBH):

$$\begin{aligned} H_{BH} = & \frac{U}{2} \sum_j b_j^\dagger b_j^\dagger b_j b_j + \sum_j b_j^\dagger b_j \left(E_0 + \hbar U_0 (V_d + c^\dagger c) J_0 \right) \\ & + \sum_j \left(b_{j+1}^\dagger b_j + b_j^\dagger b_{j+1} \right) \left(E + \hbar U_0 (V_d + c^\dagger c) J \right), \end{aligned} \quad (4.4)$$

where the first term describes the on-site two-body atom-atom interactions, the second term represents the on-site kinetic energy combined with the optical lattice potential energy, and the third term accounts for tunneling (hopping) of atoms between adjacent lattice sites. Here, U denotes the two-body interaction energy, b_j^\dagger (b_j) are bosonic creation (annihilation) operators at site j , E_0 is the on-site kinetic energy, U_0 is the optical lattice potential per photon, V_d is an additional classical potential, and J_0 is the on-site tunneling energy.

The parameters are explicitly defined as:

$$U = \frac{4\pi a_s \hbar^2}{2m} \int d^3x |\omega(x - x_j)|^4, \quad (3.3)$$

$$E_0 = \int d^3x \omega(x - x_j) \left(-\frac{\hbar^2 \nabla^2}{2m} \right) \omega(x - x_j), \quad (3.4)$$

**CHAPTER 4. BOSE-EINSTEIN CONDENSATE IN
NANO-ELECTRO-OPTOMECHANICS**

$$J_0 = \int d^3x \omega(x - x_j) \cos^2(kx) \omega(x - x_j), \quad (3.5)$$

$$U_0 = \frac{g_a^2}{\Delta_a}, \quad (3.6)$$

where a_s is the s-wave scattering length, m is the atomic mass, $\omega(x - x_j)$ is the Wannier function localized at site j , k is the cavity wave number, g_a is the atom-light coupling strength, and Δ_a is the atomic detuning. This Hamiltonian captures the interplay between atomic interactions, cavity-mediated optical potential, and atomic tunneling.

Since we are using the nearest-neighbor approximation, the tunneling term (third term in Eq. 4.4) can be neglected. Considering only the first two terms, the total Hamiltonian of the system in a frame rotating with the pump laser frequency ω_l , including the pump field ϵ_l , the weak probe field ϵ_p , and the interaction with mechanical resonators MR_1 and MR_2 , can be written as

$$H_T = \frac{U}{2} \sum_j b_j^\dagger b_j^\dagger b_j b_j + \sum_j b_j^\dagger b_j \left(E_0 + \hbar U_0 (V_d + c^\dagger c) J_0 \right) + H_{\text{fields}} + H_0 + H_{\text{coup}}, \quad (3.7)$$

where H_{fields} represents the interaction with the pump and probe fields, H_0 is the free Hamiltonian of the mechanical resonators, and H_{coup} accounts for the optomechanical and Coulomb coupling between the resonators and the cavity field.

Here, the individual contributions to the total Hamiltonian in Eq. (3.7) are explicitly written as:

$$H_0 = \hbar \Delta_c c^\dagger c, \quad (4.5)$$

$$H_{\text{coup}} = -\hbar g_{oc} c^\dagger c (b_1^\dagger + b_1) + \hbar g_c (b_1^\dagger b_2 + b_1 b_2^\dagger), \quad (4.6)$$

$$H_{\text{fields}} = i\hbar \left[\sum_{j=1}^2 \epsilon_j b_j^\dagger e^{-i\delta t} + \epsilon_l c^\dagger + \epsilon_p c^\dagger e^{-i\delta t} - \text{H.c.} \right], \quad (4.7)$$

CHAPTER 4. BOSE-EINSTEIN CONDENSATE IN NANO-ELECTRO-OPTOMECHANICS

where Δ_c is the cavity detuning, g_{oc} is the optomechanical coupling strength between the cavity and MR_1 , g_c is the Coulomb coupling between the mechanical resonators MR_1 and MR_2 , and ϵ_l , ϵ_p , ϵ_1 , and ϵ_2 represent the amplitudes of the external driving fields.

To account for dissipation and decoherence, we include the photon loss rate κ for the cavity field and the decay rate γ_b associated with the condensate mode. The resulting dynamics of the system is described by the Heisenberg-Langevin equations:

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{c} = & - \left(i\Delta_c + \frac{\kappa}{2} \right) c + ig_0(b_1^\dagger + b_1)c - iU_0J_0c \sum_j b_j^\dagger b_j \\ & + \epsilon_l + \epsilon_p e^{-i\delta t} + \sqrt{2\kappa} c_{\text{in}}(t), \end{aligned} \quad (4.8)$$

$$\dot{b}_j = \frac{E_0}{\hbar} b_j - i \frac{V_d}{\hbar} J_0 c^\dagger c b_j - \frac{U}{\hbar} b_j^\dagger b_j b_j - \gamma_b b_j + \sqrt{2\gamma_b} b_{\text{in}}(t), \quad (4.9)$$

where $c_{\text{in}}(t)$ and $b_{\text{in}}(t)$ are the noise operators associated with the input optical field and the condensate mode, respectively.

To simplify the analysis, we linearize the operators by expressing each as the sum of its steady-state value and a small fluctuation, i.e., $c = c_s + \delta c$ and $b = b_s + \delta b$. In the limit of negligible tunneling, we drop the site index j , following Refs. [64, 65]. Furthermore, we define the Hermitian quadrature operators for the mechanical mode of the condensate as

$$q = \frac{b + b^\dagger}{\sqrt{2}}, \quad p = \frac{b - b^\dagger}{i\sqrt{2}}. \quad (4.10)$$

By excluding higher-order quantum fluctuation terms, the linearized Heisenberg-Langevin equations reduce to a tractable set of equations, suitable for analyzing the dynamics of the cavity-BEC-mechanical system and its response to external driving fields [66, 67].

4.1.4 Linearized Dynamics of the System

By considering small fluctuations around the steady-state values of the operators, the linearized Heisenberg-Langevin equations for the cavity-BEC-mechanical

**CHAPTER 4. BOSE-EINSTEIN CONDENSATE IN
NANO-ELECTRO-OPTOMECHANICS**

system can be expressed in terms of the mechanical quadrature q , the cavity field fluctuation δc , and the mechanical resonator fluctuations δb_1 and δb_2 :

$$\ddot{q} + \gamma_b \dot{q} + \omega_b^2 q = -gF (\delta c + \delta c^\dagger), \quad (3.8)$$

$$\delta \dot{c} = - \left(\frac{\kappa}{2} + i\Delta \right) \delta c - igq + ig_0(b_1^\dagger + b_1)\delta c + \epsilon_l + \epsilon_p e^{-i\delta t}, \quad (3.9)$$

$$\delta \dot{b}_1 = - \left(i\omega_1 + \frac{\gamma_1}{2} \right) \delta b_1 + ig_0 c_s \delta c^\dagger + ig_0 c_s^* \delta c - ig_c \delta b_2, \quad (3.10)$$

$$\delta \dot{b}_2 = - \left(i\omega_2 + \frac{\gamma_2}{2} \right) \delta b_2 - ig_c \delta b_1, \quad (3.11)$$

where the effective cavity detuning Δ incorporates the shifts due to the BEC and mechanical resonators:

$$\Delta = \Delta_c - U_0 N J_0 - g_0 (b_{1s}^\dagger + b_{1s}) + g q_s. \quad (4.11)$$

In these equations:

- q is the Hermitian quadrature of the condensate mechanical mode. - δc represents the small fluctuations of the cavity field around its steady-state amplitude c_s . - δb_1 and δb_2 are the fluctuations of the mechanical resonators MR_1 and MR_2 , respectively. - γ_b , γ_1 , and γ_2 are the dissipation rates of the condensate and mechanical modes. - g_0 is the optomechanical coupling strength between the cavity and MR_1 , g_c is the Coulomb coupling strength between the mechanical resonators, and g is the effective coupling between the cavity and the condensate quadrature. - κ is the photon decay rate of the cavity. - F is a factor that arises from the linearization procedure and accounts for the back-action of the cavity field on the mechanical quadrature.

This set of linearized equations captures the coupled dynamics of the cavity field, mechanical resonators, and Bose-Einstein condensate, enabling detailed analysis of phenomena such as optomechanically induced transparency, mechanical cooling, and collective excitations of the condensate.

4.1.5 Definition of Key Parameters and Ansatz for Fluctuations

To analyze the linearized dynamics, we define the following system parameters:

$$\begin{aligned}
 g &= 2U_0J_0\sqrt{N}|c_s|^2, & F &= U_{\text{eff}} + v, \\
 \omega_b &= \sqrt{\langle F \rangle (v + 3U_{\text{eff}})}, & U_{\text{eff}} &= \frac{UN}{KM}, \\
 v &= U_0J_0|c_s|^2 + \frac{V_{\text{cl}}J_0}{\hbar} + \frac{E_0}{\hbar},
 \end{aligned} \tag{4.12}$$

where:

- g represents the effective optomechanical coupling between the cavity field and the condensate mode, enhanced by the mean cavity photon number $|c_s|^2$ and the total atom number N .
- F denotes the effective detuning of the condensate mode under the combined influence of atom-atom interactions and external potentials.
- ω_b is the effective mechanical frequency of the condensate mode.
- U_{eff} is the effective on-site two-body interaction energy, distributed over M lattice sites.
- v represents the combined contributions of the cavity-induced potential, classical potential V_{cl} , and on-site kinetic energy E_0 .

To solve the linearized Heisenberg-Langevin equations, we assume a harmonic time dependence for the fluctuation operators (ansatz):

$$\delta c(t) = A_1^- e^{-i\delta t} + A_1^+ e^{i\delta t}, \tag{4.13}$$

$$\delta b_1(t) = B_1^- e^{-i\delta t} + B_1^+ e^{i\delta t}, \tag{4.14}$$

$$\delta b_2(t) = B_2^- e^{-i\delta t} + B_2^+ e^{i\delta t}, \tag{4.15}$$

$$\delta q(t) = E_1^- e^{-i\delta t} + E_1^+ e^{i\delta t}, \tag{3.12}$$

where $A_1^\pm, B_1^\pm, B_2^\pm$, and E_1^\pm are the complex amplitudes of the corresponding fluctuation operators. This ansatz allows us to separate the positive- and

**CHAPTER 4. BOSE-EINSTEIN CONDENSATE IN
NANO-ELECTRO-OPTOMECHANICS**

negative-frequency components, which is essential for analyzing the system response to weak probe fields and studying phenomena such as optomechanically induced transparency and coherent oscillations in the BEC-resonator system.

4.1.6 Matrix Formulation of the Linearized System

Using the harmonic ansatz for the fluctuation operators introduced in Eq. (3.12), the linearized Heisenberg-Langevin equations (Eqs. 3.8–3.11) can be transformed into a set of coupled algebraic equations. These seven equations can be conveniently expressed in matrix form as:

$$\begin{bmatrix} h_1^+ & 0 & -iG & -iG & 0 & 0 & ig \\ 0 & h_1^- & iG^* & iG^* & 0 & 0 & -ig \\ -iG^* & -iG & h_2^+ & 0 & ig_c & 0 & 0 \\ iG^* & iG & 0 & h_2^- & 0 & -ig_c & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & ig_c & 0 & h_3^+ & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -ig_c & 0 & h_3^- & 0 \\ gF & gF & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & h_4 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} A_1^- \\ A_1^+ \\ B_1^- \\ B_1^{+*} \\ B_2^- \\ B_2^{+*} \\ E_1^- \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \epsilon_p \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad (3.13)$$

where the matrix elements are defined as:

$$\begin{aligned} h_1^\pm &= \frac{\kappa}{2} \pm i(\Delta \mp \delta), & h_2^\pm &= \frac{\gamma_1}{2} \pm i(\omega_1 \mp \delta), \\ h_3^\pm &= \frac{\gamma_2}{2} \pm i(\omega_2 \mp \delta), & h_4 &= \omega_b^2 - \delta^2 - i\delta\gamma_b, \\ G &= g_0 c_s. \end{aligned} \quad (4.16)$$

In this formulation:

- A_1^\pm , B_1^\pm , B_2^\pm , and E_1^- are the complex amplitudes of the cavity and mechanical mode fluctuations.
- κ , γ_1 , and γ_2 are the decay rates of the cavity and mechanical modes, while γ_b represents the damping of the condensate quadrature.

CHAPTER 4. BOSE-EINSTEIN CONDENSATE IN NANO-ELECTRO-OPTOMECHANICS

- Δ is the effective cavity detuning incorporating the back-action from the BEC and mechanical modes.
- g_0 is the single-photon optomechanical coupling, $G = g_0 c_s$ is the enhanced coupling at steady-state cavity amplitude c_s , and g_c is the Coulomb coupling between the mechanical resonators.
- g and F denote the effective coupling and detuning of the BEC quadrature mode, as defined previously in Eq. (4.12).

This matrix formulation allows the entire coupled system of cavity, condensate, and mechanical modes to be solved efficiently, enabling the calculation of the system's response to the weak probe field ϵ_p , including phenomena such as cavity-mediated transparency, coherent oscillations, and BEC-cavity back-action effects.

4.1.7 Solution for the Cavity Fluctuation Amplitude

By applying the Gaussian-Jordan elimination method to the system of linear equations, the amplitude of the cavity field fluctuation, denoted by A_1^- , can be explicitly determined. This amplitude represents the response of the cavity mode to the weak probe field ϵ_p in the presence of the coupled mechanical and atomic degrees of freedom. Mathematically, it is given by

$$A_1^- = \frac{M(\delta) + N(\delta) + R(\delta) + S(\delta) + T(\delta)}{X(\delta)} \epsilon_p,$$

where $M(\delta), N(\delta), R(\delta), S(\delta)$, and $T(\delta)$ are functions that incorporate the effects of optomechanical coupling, Coulomb interaction between the mechanical resonators, atomic interactions, and detunings. The denominator $X(\delta)$ accounts for the combined dynamical response of the entire system. This expression provides a compact and exact solution for the cavity fluctuation in terms of the system parameters and the probe field strength.

where the functions of the probe detuning δ are defined as:

$$\begin{aligned}
 M(\delta) &= (h_2^+ h_3^+ + g_c^2)(-g_c^2 - h_2^- h_3^-)(ig^2 F + h_1^- h_4), \\
 N(\delta) &= -|G|^2 \left[(h_2^+ - h_2^-) h_3^+ h_3^- - (h_3^+ - h_3^-) g_c^2 \right] h_4, \\
 R(\delta) &= (h_2^+ h_3^+ + g_c^2)(-g_c^2 - h_2^- h_3^-)(ih_1^+ g^2 F - ih_1^- g^2 F), \\
 S(\delta) &= -ig^2 F (G - G^*)^2 \left[(h_2^+ - h_2^-) h_3^+ h_3^- - (h_3^+ - h_3^-) g_c^2 \right], \\
 T(\delta) &= -h_1^- |G|^2 \left[(h_2^+ - h_2^-) h_3^+ h_3^- - (h_3^+ - h_3^-) g_c^2 \right],
 \end{aligned}$$

and the denominator is given by

$$X(\delta) = h_1^+ \left[h_1^- (h_2^+ h_3^+ + g_c^2)(-g_c^2 - h_2^- h_3^-) - |G|^2 \left((h_2^+ - h_2^-) h_3^+ h_3^- - (h_3^+ - h_3^-) g_c^2 \right) \right].$$

Here:

- $h_1^\pm, h_2^\pm, h_3^\pm$, and h_4 are defined in Eq. (4.16).
- $G = g_0 c_s$ is the steady-state optomechanical coupling.
- g and F correspond to the effective BEC-cavity coupling and detuning (Eq. 4.12).
- g_c is the Coulomb coupling strength between the mechanical resonators MR_1 and MR_2 .

This solution provides the explicit dependence of the cavity fluctuation amplitude A_1^- on the probe detuning δ , the optomechanical couplings, and the mechanical and condensate mode parameters. It forms the basis for analyzing transmission spectra, optomechanically induced transparency, and coherent interactions between the BEC and the mechanical resonators.

4.1.8 Output Field and Optical Response

To investigate the optical properties of the system, we employ the standard input-output formalism [68], which relates the output field $c_{\text{out}}(t)$ to the intra-

**CHAPTER 4. BOSE-EINSTEIN CONDENSATE IN
NANO-ELECTRO-OPTOMECHANICS**

cavity field $c(t)$ and the input field $c_{\text{in}}(t)$ as

$$c_{\text{out}}(t) = c_{\text{in}}(t) - \sqrt{2\kappa} c(t).$$

Using the linearized solution for the intra-cavity field, the expectation value of the output field can be written as

$$\langle c_{\text{out}}(t) \rangle = (\epsilon_l - \sqrt{2\kappa} c_s) e^{-i\omega_l t} + (\epsilon_p - \sqrt{2\kappa} c_-) e^{-i\omega_p t} - \sqrt{2\kappa} c_+ e^{-i(2\omega_l - \omega_p)t}.$$

Here, the first term represents the contribution at the pump laser frequency ω_l , the second term corresponds to the output at the probe frequency ω_p , and the third term arises from the four-wave mixing process, producing a field at the frequency $2\omega_l - \omega_p$. The real and imaginary parts of the second term describe the absorption and dispersion spectra of the probe field, respectively. This formulation allows us to analyze the optical response of the cavity under the combined influence of the pump, probe, and coupled mechanical and atomic modes.

Here, the second term corresponds to the output at the probe frequency ω_p , with detuning $\delta = \omega_p - \omega_l$. Its real and imaginary parts directly describe the absorption and dispersion spectra of the system, respectively.

By normalizing the output field with respect to the probe amplitude ϵ_p , the spectrum of the output field can be expressed as

$$\epsilon_{\text{out}} = \frac{\sqrt{2\kappa}}{\epsilon_p} A_1^-, \quad (4.17)$$

where A_1^- represents the amplitude of the cavity fluctuation at the probe frequency, obtained from the solution of the linearized Heisenberg-Langevin equations. This formulation provides a convenient means to directly analyze the optical response of the system, including the phenomena of optomechanically induced transparency, as well as the absorption and dispersion characteristics of the probe field.

4.1.9 Transmission of the Probe Field

In the above analysis, we define a convenient variable $A_1^- \equiv c_-$, which represents the cavity fluctuation amplitude at the probe frequency. Using this, the transmission of the probe field through the cavity can be expressed as [?]:

$$t_p(\omega_p) = 1 - \frac{\sqrt{2\kappa}}{\epsilon_p} A_1^-. \quad (4.18)$$

This relation provides a direct measure of the probe field response, where the magnitude and phase of $t_p(\omega_p)$ determine the absorption and dispersion characteristics of the system, respectively.

4.1.10 Experimental Parameters

For the numerical simulations and theoretical calculations, the relevant experimental parameters of the Bose-Einstein condensate are summarized in Table 4.1.

Experimental Parameters	
Parameter	Value
m_{BEC}	$1.45 \times 10^{-25} \text{ kg}$
a_{sc}	$109 a_0$
ω	38.628 kHz
N	10^5 atoms

Table 4.1: Experimental parameters used in the study, where $a_0 = 0.529 \times 10^{-10} \text{ m}$ is the Bohr radius.

4.1.11 Simulations and Electromagnetically Induced Transparency (EIT)

We consider a repulsive Bose-Einstein condensate of ^{87}Rb atoms with N two-level atoms, using experimental data from [69, 70]. The system parameters employed for the numerical simulations are taken from real experiments and

CHAPTER 4. BOSE-EINSTEIN CONDENSATE IN NANO-ELECTRO-OPTOMECHANICS

summarized in Table 4.1. Other parameters related to the optical cavity, mechanical resonators, and coupling strengths are consistent with those presented in Chapter 2.

The absorption and dispersion spectra of the EIT window are calculated numerically by analyzing the real and imaginary components of the output field. The results reveal a characteristic three-resonance structure in the EIT window, which closely resembles the behavior observed in two-level atomic systems interacting with a two-mode optomechanical cavity[71]. The outer dips of the transparency window arise from the combined effects of optomechanical and Coulomb couplings, while the central resonance is primarily due to the atomic coupling within the condensate.

The left and right dips in the transparency window are attributed to the combined effects of optomechanical coupling g_0 and Coulomb coupling g_c , whereas the central dip corresponds to the atomic coupling g of the Bose-Einstein condensate. These results demonstrate that the NEOMS-BEC system exhibits tunable transparency, which can be controlled by adjusting the respective coupling strengths.

(a) EIT photon number (arbitrary units) vs normalized detuning δ/ω_1 , for $g_0 = 2 \times 4$ kHz, $g_c = 0.2$ MHz, and $g = 2 \times 40$ kHz.

(b) EIT photon number (arbitrary units) vs normalized detuning δ/ω_1 , for $g_0 = 2 \times 4$ kHz, $g_c = 0.2$ MHz, and $g = 2 \times 40$ kHz.

Figure 4.2: Absorption and dispersion spectra of the EIT window as a function of normalized detuning δ/ω_1 .

4.1.12 Slow Light in Bose-Einstein Condensates

Bose-Einstein condensates (BECs) provide an ideal platform for studying Electromagnetically Induced Transparency (EIT). EIT enables a normally opaque atomic medium to become transparent to a weak probe field due to quantum interference effects. When a probe pulse propagates through such a medium, its group velocity can be dramatically reduced—a phenomenon known as *slow light*.

The group velocity of a light pulse is determined by the dispersive properties of the medium, specifically the variation of the refractive index with frequency. In EIT media, the steep dispersion around the transparency window leads to a substantial reduction in group velocity, allowing the pulse to propagate very slowly compared to its speed in vacuum. The refractive index and its dispersion can be analyzed using the phase spectrum of the transmitted or reflected probe field [72, 73].

In a landmark experiment, Hau *et al.* [74] observed a group velocity as low as 17 m/s in a sodium atomic gas cooled well below the BEC transition temperature ($T_c \approx 435$ nK). Slow light has important applications in optical information processing, including optical switches, high-resolution spectroscopy, frequency sensing, and quantum memory devices [75].

Simulations

We now investigate the slow light effect in the proposed nano-electro-optomechanical system (NEOMS) by analyzing the group delay of the transmitted optical field. The group delay at probe frequency ω_p is defined as

$$\tau = \left. \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial \omega_p} \right|_{\omega_p}, \quad (4.19)$$

where $\phi(\omega_p) = \arg[t_p(\omega_p)]$ is the phase of the transmitted field. The transmission and reflection group delays can also be expressed as

**CHAPTER 4. BOSE-EINSTEIN CONDENSATE IN
NANO-ELECTRO-OPTOMECHANICS**

$$\tau = \text{Im} \left[\frac{1}{\varepsilon} \frac{\partial \varepsilon}{\partial \omega_p} \right], \quad (3.17)$$

$$\tau = \text{Re} \left[\frac{1}{\varepsilon} \frac{\partial \varepsilon}{\partial \omega_p} \right], \quad (3.18)$$

where $\tau < 0$ corresponds to fast (superluminal) light, and $\tau > 0$ indicates slow (subluminal) light propagation.

The transmission phase spectrum is calculated using the argument of the transmitted field. Within the EIT transparency window, the transmitted phase exhibits a sharp variation, indicating a significant reduction in the group velocity [76]. In the presence of a BEC, the phase changes more rapidly near the resonance of the transparency window, demonstrating enhanced control over the group velocity.

Figure 4.3: Transmission phase $\phi(\omega_p)$ vs normalized detuning δ/ω_1 .

For detuning near the mechanical resonance ($\delta \approx \omega_1$), the steep phase variation strongly modifies the group index of the medium, leading to significant changes in the pulse propagation velocity.

In Figure 4.4, the group delay τ is plotted as a function of the pump power P_l at $\delta = \omega_1$ and $\Delta = \omega_1$, for different cavity decay rates κ . It is evident that the magnitude of the group delay increases as κ decreases, indicating that the

CHAPTER 4. BOSE-EINSTEIN CONDENSATE IN NANO-ELECTRO-OPTOMECHANICS

Figure 4.4: Group delay τ (μ s) vs pump power P_l (mW) for cavity decay rates $\kappa = 2\pi \times 215$ kHz and $\kappa = 3\pi \times 215$ kHz.

system is robust against cavity losses. Longer mechanical lifetimes result in a more pronounced slow-light effect.

4.2 Conclusion

In this chapter, we have studied the dynamics of a Bose-Einstein condensate (BEC) trapped inside a nano-electro-optomechanical system (NEOMS) and analyzed its impact on the optical properties of the cavity. Using the optomechanical Bose-Hubbard Hamiltonian and linearized Heisenberg-Langevin equations, we derived the probe transmission and output field spectra, including the effects of mechanical resonators and cavity-BEC coupling.

Our numerical simulations reveal clear signatures of electromagnetically induced transparency (EIT) in both the absorption and dispersion spectra. The presence of the BEC introduces additional control over the transparency window, with the optomechanical and Coulomb couplings generating multiple resonance points. These features highlight the interplay between atomic, optical, and mechanical degrees of freedom in NEOMS.

Furthermore, we investigated the slow light effect by analyzing the phase response and group delay of the transmitted probe field. The results demonstrate that the group velocity of light can be significantly reduced within the EIT window, and the magnitude of slow light is strongly enhanced in the presence of the BEC. The simulations also show that the system is robust against cavity losses, and longer mechanical lifetimes lead to more pronounced subluminal propagation.

Overall, this study confirms that BEC-based nano-electro-optomechanical systems provide an ideal platform for exploring quantum optical phenomena such as EIT and slow light. The tunable interaction strengths and multiple resonance features offer new opportunities for optical information processing, quantum memory applications, and precision control of light-matter interactions at the quantum level.

Chapter 5

Conclusion

We introduce a robust method for practically realizing optical switches using a nano-electro-opto-mechanical system (NEOMS). This complex setup comprises an optical resonator and two interconnected moving mirrors influenced by the electrostatic Coulomb force. Our study reveals optical and mirror bistability patterns, shaped by input laser power, coupling frequencies, and external mechanical influences on the mirrors. We explore the system's resilience and dynamic control by manipulating the mirrors' mechanical motion to influence the optical cavity field, and vice versa. By adjusting parameters like amplitude and phase angle, we selectively drive the mechanical resonators. We investigate optical bistability under varying conditions, including optomechanical and Coulomb coupling frequencies, and cavity detuning. Our findings demonstrate the controllable manipulation of steady-state photon bistability through input laser power adjustments. Furthermore, we report successful control of optical bistability using external mechanical driving fields on the mirrors. This control is achieved by selectively driving one of the mechanical pumps, enhancing the steady-state photon count and improving mirror motion. The amplitude and phase adjustments of external mechanical inputs influence the phase-sensitive bistability of static photon counts. Our study also uncovers mirror bistability influenced by optomechanical and Coulomb coupling strengths. Stable branches of bistable curves overlap at different mirror field coupling frequencies. The introduction of external mechanical driving fields results in the suppression and enhancement of mirror displacement

CHAPTER 5. CONCLUSION

bistability. The combination of coupling frequency, switchable mechanical driving fields, cavity field detuning, and threshold laser power enables the development of adjustable optical switches and all-optical transistors. This work lays the foundation for potential extensions, including the achievement of multistable behaviors in both static photon intensity and mirror displacement.

Appendix A

Bistability Simulation Code

A.1 Python Implementation

```
1 import numpy as np
2 import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
3
4 # -----
5 # 1. Physical and system parameters
6 # -----
7 w1 = 2 * np.pi * 947e3
8 w2 = w1
9 k = 2 * np.pi * 215e3
10
11 g1 = w1 / 6700
12 g2 = g1
13 m1 = 149e-12
14 m2 = m1
15
16 yc = 1064e-9
17 c = 3e8
18
19 wc = (2 * np.pi * c) / yc
20 L = 25e-3
```

APPENDIX

```
21
22 g_c = 0.2e6
23 h_cut = 1.054e-34
24 g0 = np.sqrt((h_cut / (2 * m1 * w1))) * wc / L
25
26 G = np.sqrt(2 * h_cut * w1 * m1) * wc / L
27 G0 = G / h_cut
28
29 gc = h_cut * g_c
30 e_L = 2 * np.pi * 250e3
31 Δ_c = w1
32 wL = wc - Δ_c
33
34 # -----
35 # 2. Solve system steady-state coefficients
36 # -----
37 s1 = (1j * w1 + g1 / 2) * (1j * w2 + g2 / 2) + gc**2
38 s2 = np.conj(s1)
39
40 r1 = g0 * (((1j * w2 + g2 / 2) / s1) + ((-1j * w2 + g2 ...
    / 2) / s2))
41 r2 = 1j * g0 * gc * (1 / s2 - 1 / s1)
42 r3 = 1j * g0 * (((1j * w2 + g2 / 2) / s1) - ((-1j * w2 ...
    + g2 / 2) / s2))
43
44 beta = e_L ** 2
45
46 # Optional mechanical drive terms (set to zero)
47 knock_1 = 0.0 * 200000000 * w1
48 knock_2 = 0.0 * w2
49
50 # -----
51 # 3. Steady-state polynomial coefficients
52 # -----
53 a1 = abs(r3**2)
```

APPENDIX

```
54 a2 = -abs(2 * r3 * ( $\Delta_c$  - r1 * knock_2))
55 a3 = (abs( $\Delta_c$  - r1 * knock_1 - r2 * knock_2)) ** 2 + ...
    k**2 / 4
56
57 # -----
58 # 4. Bistability curve calculation
59 # -----
60 x = np.arange(0, 140e10, 0.0001e10)
61 exx = (h_cut * wL / k) * (a1 * x**3 + a2 * x**2 + a3 * x)
62 y = 10 * exx
63
64 lev1 = 3.5e11
65 lev2 = 10e11
66
67 aboveLine = (x > lev1) & (x  $\leq$  lev2)
68 bottomLine = x.copy(); bottomLine[aboveLine] = np.nan
69 topLine = x.copy(); topLine[ $\neg$ aboveLine] = np.nan
70
71 # -----
72 # 5. Plotting results
73 # -----
74 plt.plot(y, bottomLine, 'k', linewidth=1.6, ...
    label="Stable Region")
75 plt.plot(y, topLine, 'b--', linewidth=1.6, ...
    label="Unstable Region")
76
77 plt.xlabel(r' $\wp_1$  (mW)', fontsize=16, ...
    fontname='Times New Roman')
78 plt.ylabel(r' $|c_s|^2$ ', fontsize=16, fontname='Times ...
    New Roman')
79 plt.axis([0, 8, 0, 140e10])
80 plt.grid(True)
81 plt.legend()
82 plt.title("Optical Bistability in a Hybrid ...
    Optomechanical System", fontsize=14)
```

APPENDIX

```
83  
84 plt.show()
```

Listing 1: Python code for plotting the bistability curve

Bibliography

- [1] JS Al-Khalili, JA Tostevin, and IJ Thompson. Radii of halo nuclei from cross section measurements. *Physical review C*, 54(4):1843, 1996.
- [2] Sohail Ahmed, Asma Javaid, Hui Jing, and Farhan Saif. Engineering optical and mirror bi-stability mechanically. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2307.05723*, 2023.
- [3] Abid Ali, Farhan Saif, and Hiroki Saito. Phase separation and multistability of a two-component bose-einstein condensate in an optical cavity. *Physical Review A*, 105(6):063318, 2022.
- [4] A Dorsel, John D McCullen, Pierre Meystre, E Vignes, and H Walther. Optical bistability and mirror confinement induced by radiation pressure. *Physical Review Letters*, 51(17):1550, 1983.
- [5] Pierre Meystre, EM Wright, JD McCullen, and E Vignes. Theory of radiation-pressure-driven interferometers. *JOSA B*, 2(11):1830–1840, 1985.
- [6] Human Microbiome Project Consortium. Structure, function and diversity of the healthy human microbiome. *Nature*, 486(7402):207–214, 2012.
- [7] M Pinard, C Fabre, S Bourzeix, A Heidmann, E Giacobino, and S Reynaud. Quantum noise reduction using a cavity with a movable mirror. In *European Quantum Electronics Conference*, page QWD1. Optica Publishing Group, 1994.
- [8] David Vitali, Paolo Tombesi, MJ Woolley, AC Doherty, and GJ Milburn. Entangling a nanomechanical resonator and a superconducting microwave cavity. *Physical Review A*, 76(4):042336, 2007.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- [9] Claudiu Genes, A Mari, P Tombesi, and D Vitali. Robust entanglement of a micromechanical resonator with output optical fields. *Physical Review A*, 78(3):032316, 2008.
- [10] M Abdi, Sh Barzanjeh, P Tombesi, and D Vitali. Effect of phase noise on the generation of stationary entanglement in cavity optomechanics. *Physical Review A*, 84(3):032325, 2011.
- [11] Alexander Carmele, Berit Vogell, Kai Stannigel, and Peter Zoller. Opto-nanomechanics strongly coupled to a rydberg superatom: coherent versus incoherent dynamics. *New Journal of Physics*, 16(6):063042, 2014.
- [12] Benjamin Rogers, N Lo Gullo, Gabriele De Chiara, G Massimo Palma, and Mauro Paternostro. Hybrid optomechanics for quantum technologies. *Quantum Measurements and Quantum Metrology*, 2(1):000010247820140002, 2014.
- [13] F Bariani, S Singh, LF Buchmann, M Vengalattore, and P Meystre. Hybrid optomechanical cooling by atomic λ systems. *Physical Review A*, 90(3):033838, 2014.
- [14] AH Safavi-Naeini, TP Mayer, J Chan, and M Eichen. eld, m. winger, q. lin, jt hill, de chang and o. painter. *Nature*, 472:69–73, 2011.
- [15] T Rocheleau, T Ndukum, C Macklin, and JB Hertzberg. Aa clerk, and kc schwab. *Nature*, 463:72, 2010.
- [16] Keith C Schwab and Michael L Roukes. Putting mechanics into quantum mechanics. *Physics Today*, 58(7):36–42, 2005.
- [17] SA McGee, D Meiser, CA Regal, KW Lehnert, and MJ Holland. Mechanical resonators for storage and transfer of electrical and optical quantum states. *Physical Review A*, 87(5):053818, 2013.
- [18] Muhammad Javed Akram and Farhan Saif. Complex dynamics of nano-mechanical membrane in cavity optomechanics. *Nonlinear Dynamics*, 83:963–970, 2016.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- [19] JM Fink, M Göppl, M Baur, R Bianchetti, Peter J Leek, Alexandre Blais, and Andreas Wallraff. Climbing the jaynes–cummings ladder and observing its nonlinearity in a cavity qed system. *Nature*, 454(7202):315–318, 2008.
- [20] Lin Tian. Optoelectromechanical transducer: Reversible conversion between microwave and optical photons. *Annalen der Physik*, 527(1-2):1–14, 2015.
- [21] Lin Tian and Peter Zoller. Coupled ion-nanomechanical systems. *Physical review letters*, 93(26):266403, 2004.
- [22] Steven D Bennett, Jesse Maassen, and Aashish A Clerk. Scattering approach to backaction in coherent nanoelectromechanical systems. *Physical review letters*, 105(21):217206, 2010.
- [23] David J Wineland, Christopher Monroe, Wayne M Itano, Dietrich Leibfried, Brian E King, and Dawn M Meekhof. Experimental issues in coherent quantum-state manipulation of trapped atomic ions. *Journal of research of the National Institute of Standards and Technology*, 103(3):259, 1998.
- [24] A Szöke, V Daneu, J Goldhar, and NA Kurnit. Bistable optical element and its applications. *Applied Physics Letters*, 15(11):376–379, 1969.
- [25] Kashif Ammar Yasir and Wu-Ming Liu. Tunable bistability in hybrid bose-einstein condensate optomechanics. *Scientific reports*, 5(1):10612, 2015.
- [26] A Dalafi, MH Naderi, M Soltanolkotabi, and Sh Barzanjeh. Controllability of optical bistability, cooling and entanglement in hybrid cavity optomechanical systems by nonlinear atom–atom interaction. *Journal of Physics B: Atomic, Molecular and Optical Physics*, 46(23):235502, 2013.
- [27] Qing Sun, Xing-Hua Hu, WM Liu, XC Xie, and An-Chun Ji. Effect on cavity optomechanics of the interaction between a cavity field and a one-dimensional interacting bosonic gas. *Physical Review A*, 84(2):023822, 2011.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- [28] Suzhen Zhang, Jiahua Li, Rong Yu, Wei Wang, and Ying Wu. Optical multistability and fano line-shape control via mode coupling in whispering-gallery-mode microresonator optomechanics. *Scientific Reports*, 7(1):39781, 2017.
- [29] Kamran Ullah. Electro-optomechanical switch via tunable bistability and four-wave mixing. *Chinese Physics B*, 28(11):114209, 2019.
- [30] Hyatt Gibbs. *Optical bistability: controlling light with light*. Elsevier, 2012.
- [31] Shum Ping, Lu Chao, et al. Bistability threshold inside hysteresis loop of nonlinear fiber bragg gratings. *Optics Express*, 13(13):5127–5135, 2005.
- [32] APH Gonzalez-Marcos, A Hurtado, and J Antonio Martin-Pereda. Optical bistable devices as sensing elements. In *Unmanned/Unattended Sensors and Sensor Networks*, volume 5611, pages 63–70. SPIE, 2004.
- [33] Steven D Bennett, Lynda Cockins, Yoichi Miyahara, Peter Grütter, and Aashish A Clerk. Strong electromechanical coupling of an atomic force microscope cantilever to a quantum dot. *Physical review letters*, 104(1):017203, 2010.
- [34] Kwan H Lee, Terry G McRae, Glen I Harris, Joachim Knittel, and Warwick P Bowen. Cooling and control of a cavity optoelectromechanical system. *Physical Review Letters*, 104(12):123604, 2010.
- [35] Ying-Dan Wang and Aashish A Clerk. Using dark modes for high-fidelity optomechanical quantum state transfer. *New Journal of Physics*, 14(10):105010, 2012.
- [36] Colm Ryan and Hanhee Paik. Superconducting qubit optical transducer (sqot). Technical report, Raytheon BBN Technologies Corp., Cambridge, United States, 2015.
- [37] Terry G McRae, Kwan H Lee, Glen I Harris, Joachim Knittel, and Warwick P Bowen. Cavity optoelectromechanical system combining strong electrical actuation with ultrasensitive transduction. *Physical Review A*, 82(2):023825, 2010.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- [38] Qiang Lin, Jessie Rosenberg, Darrick Chang, Ryan Camacho, Matt Eichenfield, Kerry J Vahala, and Oskar Painter. Coherent mixing of mechanical excitations in nano-optomechanical structures. *Nature Photonics*, 4(4):236–242, 2010.
- [39] Francesco Massel, Sung Un Cho, Juha-Matti Pirkkalainen, Pertti J Hakonen, Tero T Heikkilä, and Mika A Sillanpää. Multimode circuit optomechanics near the quantum limit. *Nature communications*, 3(1):987, 2012.
- [40] Arne Barfuss, Jean Teissier, Elke Neu, Andreas Nunnenkamp, and Patrick Maletinsky. Strong mechanical driving of a single electron spin. *Nature Physics*, 11(10):820–824, 2015.
- [41] Inah Yeo, Pierre-Louis de Assis, Arnaud Gloppe, Eva Dupont-Ferrier, Pierre Verlot, Nitin S Malik, Emmanuel Dupuy, Julien Claudon, Jean-Michel Gérard, Alexia Auffèves, et al. Strain-mediated coupling in a quantum dot–mechanical oscillator hybrid system. *Nature nanotechnology*, 9(2):106–110, 2014.
- [42] AA Clerk, X Waintal, and PW Brouwer. Fano resonances as a probe of phase coherence in quantum dots. *Physical review letters*, 86(20):4636, 2001.
- [43] M Vengalattore, M Hafezi, MD Lukin, and M Prentiss. Optical bistability at low light level due to collective atomic recoil. *Physical review letters*, 101(6):063901, 2008.
- [44] Ferdinand Brennecke, Stephan Ritter, Tobias Donner, and Tilman Esslinger. Cavity optomechanics with a bose-einstein condensate. *Science*, 322(5899):235–238, 2008.
- [45] Tom P Purdy, DWC Brooks, Thierry Botter, Nathan Brahms, Z-Y Ma, and Dan M Stamper-Kurn. Tunable cavity optomechanics with ultracold atoms. *Physical review letters*, 105(13):133602, 2010.
- [46] Roohollah Ghobadi, AR Bahrapour, and C Simon. Quantum optomechanics in the bistable regime. *Physical Review A*, 84(3):033846, 2011.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- [47] Eyob A Sete, H Eleuch, and Sumanta Das. Semiconductor cavity qed with squeezed light: Nonlinear regime. *Physical Review A*, 84(5):053817, 2011.
- [48] Cheng Jiang, Hongxiang Liu, Yuanshun Cui, Xiaowei Li, Guibin Chen, and Xuemin Shuai. Controllable optical bistability based on photons and phonons in a two-mode optomechanical system. *Physical Review A*, 88(5):055801, 2013.
- [49] Nan Xu, Ze-Di Cheng, Jin-Dao Tang, Xiao-Min Lv, Tong Li, Meng-Lin Guo, You Wang, Hai-Zhi Song, Qiang Zhou, and Guang-Wei Deng. Recent advances in nano-opto-electro-mechanical systems. *Nanophotonics*, 10(9):2265–2281, 2021.
- [50] Tian-Xiang Lu, Ya-Feng Jiao, Hui-Lai Zhang, Farhan Saif, and Hui Jing. Selective and switchable optical amplification with mechanical driven oscillators. *Phys. Rev. A*, 100:013813, Jul 2019.
- [51] Sebastian G Hofer and Klemens Hammerer. Quantum control of optomechanical systems. In *Advances in Atomic, Molecular, and Optical Physics*, volume 66, pages 263–374. Elsevier, 2017.
- [52] Michel Pinard, Y Hadjar, and Antoine Heidmann. Effective mass in quantum effects of radiation pressure. *The European Physical Journal D-Atomic, Molecular, Optical and Plasma Physics*, 7:107–116, 1999.
- [53] DF Walls and Gerard J Milburn. Bose-einstein condensation. In *Quantum Optics*, pages 397–420. Springer, 2008.
- [54] William D Phillips. Nobel lecture: Laser cooling and trapping of neutral atoms. *Reviews of Modern Physics*, 70(3):721, 1998.
- [55] Philippe Bouyer, Vincent Boyer, SG Murdoch, Guillaume Delannoy, Yann Le Coq, Alain Aspect, and Michel Lécrivain. Rf-induced evaporative cooling and bec in a high magnetic field. In *Bose-Einstein Condensates and Atom Lasers*, pages 165–186. Springer, 2000.
- [56] Giuseppe Smirne. *Experiments with Bose-Einstein condensates in optical traps*. PhD thesis, University of Oxford, 2005.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- [57] Philip Ball. Cool atoms make physics prize matter. *Nature*, 413(6856):554–554, 2001.
- [58] Benjamin Deissler. *A magnetic trap for evaporative cooling of Rb atoms*. PhD thesis, University of Virginia, 2003.
- [59] Wolfgang Ketterle. Nobel lecture: When atoms behave as waves: Bose-einstein condensation and the atom laser. *Reviews of Modern Physics*, 74(4):1131, 2002.
- [60] Keir C Neuman and Steven M Block. Optical trapping. *Review of scientific instruments*, 75(9):2787–2809, 2004.
- [61] Jonathan P Marangos. Electromagnetically induced transparency. *Journal of modern optics*, 45(3):471–503, 1998.
- [62] Zachary John Dutton. *Ultraslow, stopped, and compressed light in Bose-Einstein condensates*. Harvard University, 2002.
- [63] Till D Kühner, Steven R White, and Hartmut Monien. One-dimensional bose-hubbard model with nearest-neighbor interaction. *Physical Review B*, 61(18):12474, 2000.
- [64] Luis Lafuente and José A Cuesta. Density functional theory for nearest-neighbor exclusion lattice gases in two and three dimensions. *Physical Review E*, 68(6):066120, 2003.
- [65] M Javed Akram, Fazal Ghafoor, M Miskeen Khan, and Farhan Saif. Fano resonances control and slow light with bose-einstein condensate in a nano cavity. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1512.07278*, 2015.
- [66] Aranya B Bhattacharjee. Cavity quantum optomechanics of ultracold atoms in an optical lattice: normal-mode splitting. *Physical Review A—Atomic, Molecular, and Optical Physics*, 80(4):043607, 2009.
- [67] M Javed Akram, M Miskeen Khan, and Farhan Saif. Tunable fast and slow light in a hybrid optomechanical system. *Physical Review A*, 92(2):023846, 2015.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- [68] Amir H Safavi-Naeini, TP Mayer Alegre, Jasper Chan, Matt Eichenfield, Martin Winger, Qiang Lin, Jeff T Hill, Darrick E Chang, and Oskar Painter. Electromagnetically induced transparency and slow light with optomechanics. *Nature*, 472(7341):69–73, 2011.
- [69] Cristian Huepe, Stéphane Metens, Guy Dewel, Pierre Borckmans, and Marc-Etienne Brachet. Decay rates in attractive bose-einstein condensates. *Physical review letters*, 82(8):1616, 1999.
- [70] J Söding, D Guéry-Odelin, P Desbiolles, F Chevy, H Inamori, and J Dalibard. Three-body decay of a rubidium bose–einstein condensate. *Applied physics B*, 69(4):257–261, 1999.
- [71] Cheng Jiang, Hongxiang Liu, Yuanshun Cui, Xiaowei Li, Guibin Chen, and Bin Chen. Electromagnetically induced transparency and slow light in two-mode optomechanics. *Optics express*, 21(10):12165–12173, 2013.
- [72] WZ Jia, LF Wei, Yong Li, and Yu-xi Liu. Phase-dependent optical response properties in an optomechanical system by coherently driving the mechanical resonator. *Physical Review A*, 91(4):043843, 2015.
- [73] Zhilei Huang, Kaiyu Cui, Guoren Bai, Xue Feng, Fang Liu, Wei Zhang, and Yidong Huang. High-mechanical-frequency characteristics of optomechanical crystal cavity with coupling waveguide. *Scientific Reports*, 6(1):34160, 2016.
- [74] Chien Liu, Zachary Dutton, Cyrus H Behroozi, and Lene Vestergaard Hau. Observation of coherent optical information storage in an atomic medium using halted light pulses. *Nature*, 409(6819):490–493, 2001.
- [75] Joseph A Yasi. Quantum information storage with slow and stopped light.
- [76] Peter W Milonni. *Fast light, slow light and left-handed light*. CRC Press, 2004.